

**IN THE COURT OF COMMON PLEAS
FRANKLIN COUNTY, OHIO**

LVNV FUNDING, LLC.)	
)	Case No. 24CV000841
Plaintiff,)	JUDGE LYNCH
)	
V)	<u>PLAINTIFF'S NOTICE OF FILING</u>
)	<u>EXHIBITS IN SUPPORT OF MOTION</u>
ERIC WISEMAN,)	<u>FOR SUMMARY JUDGMENT AS TO</u>
)	<u>COMPLAINT AND COUNTERCLAIM</u>
Defendant.)	

Now comes Plaintiff and respectfully gives notice of the filing of Plaintiff's discovery responses for use in support Plaintiff's Motion for Summary Judgment

Respectfully submitted,

/s/Boyd W. Gentry
Boyd W. Gentry (0071057)
Law Office of Boyd W. Gentry, LLC
4031 Colonel Glenn Highway, First Floor
Dayton, OH 45431
Tel. 937.839.2881
bgentry@boydgentrylaw.com
Attorney for Plaintiff as to Counterclaim Only

/s/Gina Nennig
Gina Nennig, Esq.
Stenger & Stenger, P.C.
Attorneys for Plaintiff
2618 East Paris Avenue SE
Grand Rapids, MI 49546
Court Inquiries Ph: (877) 988-2280
Defendant/Counsel Ph: (888) 305-7775
ohio@stengerlaw.com

CERTIFICATE OF SERVICE

A copy of the foregoing was duly served upon Attorney for Defendant, Andrew Barnes,
by email barnes@abarneslaw.com on this 17th day of March 2025.

/s/Boyd W. Gentry
Boyd W. Gentry (0071057)

**IN THE COURT OF COMMON PLEAS
FRANKLIN COUNTY, OHIO**

LVNV FUNDING, LLC

*

CASE NO. 24CV000841

PLAINTIFF

v.

*

**PLAINTIFF'S RESPONSES TO
DEFENDANT'S
INTERROGATORIES**

ERIC WISEMAN

DEFENDANT

*

Now comes Plaintiff, by counsel, and provides the following responses to Defendant's interrogatories.

INTERROGATORY NO. 1: State the name(s), business address(es) and job title(s) or capacity(ies) of the officer(s), employee(s) or agent(s) answering or providing any information used to answer each Interrogatory.

RESPONSE: Lacey Pearce, Authorized Representative for LVNV Funding, LLC, and Paralegal, Resurgent Capital Services, LP, PO Box 10497 Greenville, SC 29603

INTERROGATORY NO. 2: State the correct legal name of your organization.

RESPONSE: LVNV Funding, LLC

INTERROGATORY NO. 3: State any other names which your organization uses to identify itself.

RESPONSE: None

INTERROGATORY NO. 4: Identify and describe with particularity each document known to Plaintiff which is related to the debt of Defendant for which you are suing.

RESPONSE: Objection. The definition of “identify” is overly broad and unduly burdensome. Without waiving objections, see the documents produced here and labeled LVNV1-78. Those documents are business records made by, or from information transmitted by, a person with knowledge of the events described therein, at or near the time of the event described, were kept in the ordinary course of the regularly conducted business activity of such persons, and it is the regular practice of those business activities to make and rely upon such records. These records have been incorporated into the business records of LVNV and are routinely relied upon by LVNV in conducting business. The documents attached thereto are business records of LVNV that are maintained on behalf of LVNV and are kept and maintained in the course of regularly conducted business activity. Those documents are a compilation of the information provided upon acquisition and information obtained since acquisition.

Those documents show that the Account was originated by Cross River Bank for the benefit and use of Defendant. See LVNV1-47. Defendant did not make the necessary or minimum payments on the Account, leaving an outstanding balance as alleged in the Complaint. Plaintiff is the current owner of the Account. As shown in LVNV47-78, Plaintiff acquired all ownership rights in the Account, including the right to collect the current balance alleged in the Complaint, plus any other relief the court awards. See the documents produced here and labeled LVNV1-78. Those documents are incorporated herein by reference pursuant to Civ. R. 33(C).

INTERROGATORY NO. 5: State the name(s) and address(es) of Plaintiff's liability insurer(s) for the last three years and the dates of coverage, type, policy number(s) of each liability insurance policy.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is beyond the scope of discovery as no insurance claim was made for this matter.

INTERROGATORY NO. 6: If you have made a demand for payment from Defendant, then give the date on which you made the demand, the amount you demanded, and identify with specificity all documents which reflect the demand.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. It does not relate to any claim or defense. Without waiving objections, Plaintiff did not direct any communications to Defendant. Plaintiff never called Defendant on the telephone.

INTERROGATORY NO. 7: If you contend that a third party made a demand for payment from Defendant, then give the date on which the demand was made, the amount demanded, and identify all documents which reflect the demand.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. It does not relate to any claim or defense.

INTERROGATORY NO. 8: State the total amount of principal that you contend Defendant borrowed from the Original Creditor, giving the date and amount on which, each principal sum was borrowed, and identify the goods or services that Defendant purchased.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 show the detailed responsive information.

INTERROGATORY NO. 9: State the amount of interest that was charged to Defendant pursuant to each principal sum that was borrowed and describe the manner in which you calculated the interest.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 show the detailed responsive information.

INTERROGATORY NO. 10: As of the date that you filed this lawsuit, state how much of the amount you demanded was principal and how much was interest and explain the basis of your calculations by making specific reference to the documents on which your calculations are based.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-63 show the detailed responsive information.

INTERROGATORY NO. 11: State with specificity the amount of each late fee, over-limit fee, membership fee, application fee, or any fee that was ever assessed against Defendant with respect to Defendant's Account.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 show the detailed responsive information.

INTERROGATORY NO. 12: Describe the exact consideration paid by you to acquire Defendant's Account. If all or part of the consideration was money, state the exact sum

of money that was paid by you for the assignment to you of Defendant's Account, from whom it was paid, to whom it was paid, the date it was paid, and identify all documents which reflect the consideration and the items purchased.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request is not related to any claim or defense. This request seeks to harass, oppress, and annoy because it knowingly calls for sensitive and competitive business information that has nothing to do with this case. The amount paid by an assignee for an otherwise enforceable account is legally irrelevant.

INTERROGATORY NO. 13: As of the date of your answers to these Interrogatories, state the total amount of money you claim that Defendant owes to you, and state the specific amount of that money that constitutes principal, interest, late fees, over-limit fees, application fees, membership fees, collection fees, any other fees, and court costs.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 show the detailed responsive information.

INTERROGATORY NO. 14: List and identify with particularity every document that supports your calculation of the figures responsive to the previous Interrogatory, and identify every document that authorizes you to collect these amounts; give a detailed description of how you calculated these figures, and identify every individual who has personal knowledge of the accuracy of these figures and/or who has personal knowledge that the figures were accurately calculated or determined.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-63 show the detailed responsive information. Ms. Lacey

Pearce is an authorized representative of Plaintiff and can testify as to the contents of those business records.

INTERROGATORY NO. 15: Identify with particularity all documents you claim entitle you to ownership of the Account.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 show that Plaintiff is the owner of the account.

INTERROGATORY NO. 16: Identify with particularity all documents you claim entitle you to collect any amount, including interest, other than the principal amount of the debt.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 show the detailed responsive information.

INTERROGATORY NO. 17: Identify with particularity all documents related to the debt or Account that contain Defendant's signature.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 show the detailed responsive information.

INTERROGATORY NO. 18: Identify the date the Account was put into collections, and with whom.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request is not related to any claim or defense.

INTERROGATORY NO. 19: Identify all previous owners of the Account that you are seeking to collect upon.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 show the previous owners as Cross River Bank, MPLI Capital Holdings II, Sherman Originator III LLC, and Sherman Originator LLC. All rights and title to the account were transferred and assigned to LVNV Funding, LLC as shown in LVNV65-78.

INTERROGATORY NO. 20: Identify all previous assignees of the Account you are seeking to collect upon.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 show the account was originated by as Cross River Bank, then assigned to MPLI Capital Holdings II, then assigned to Sherman Originator III LLC, and then assigned to Sherman Originator LLC, ultimately thereafter being assigned to Plaintiff LVNV Funding, LLC. All rights and title to the account were transferred and assigned to LVNV Funding, LLC which still holds such rights and title to the account as shown in LVNV65-78.

INTERROGATORY NO. 21: Identify with particularity anyone other than Plaintiff who has a legal, equitable, or beneficial interest in the debt you are seeking in this matter.

RESPONSE: No other person or entity has such an interest.

INTERROGATORY NO. 22: With respect to Defendant's Account, do you contend that Defendant was in default on any payments owed to the Original Creditor or anyone else?

If your answer is "yes," give each date on which you contend Defendant was in default and state the amount by which Defendant was in default as of that date.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 provide the detailed responsive information.

INTERROGATORY NO. 23: For each default listed in your response to the preceding interrogatory, are you aware of any notice of default that was provided to Defendant? If your answer is "yes," describe the contents of the notice of default, identify the person or entity who sent it, state the date on which it was given, state the address to which it was sent, and identify with particularity all documents which support your contention that a notice of default was given.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 provide the detailed responsive information.

INTERROGATORY NO. 24: Identify and describe with particularity the terms of the agreement between Defendant and the Original Creditor and/or any Intervening Creditor pursuant to which Plaintiff seeks to collect on this Account from Defendant.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-46 show the terms of the agreement with the original creditor and Plaintiff (because Plaintiff received an assignment of the account and thus, stands in the shoes of the original creditor).

INTERROGATORY NO. 25: Identify by name, position, address and phone number all persons or person who have interacted with the alleged Defendant's account, or had

debt collections attempts to the Defendant.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request is not related to any claim or defense.

INTERROGATORY NO. 26: Identify all documents that are related to, connected to, or a part of the alleged Defendant's Account.

RESPONSE: In accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 33(C), the business records attached hereto as LVNV1-78 are the account records.

INTERROGATORY NO. 27: Identify with particularity each person whom the Plaintiff expects to call as an expert witness at trial, state the subject matter on which the expert is expected to testify and the substance of the facts and opinions to which the expert is expected to testify, and a summary of the grounds for each opinion.

RESPONSE: N/A

INTERROGATORY NO. 28: Do you have any evidence of when the Account which is the subject of this lawsuit was assigned to you and/or referred to you and/or acquired by you, and, if so, explain and describe that evidence in detail.

RESPONSE: Yes, the attached documents show the ownership rights in the Account were assigned to, transferred to, and became vested in Plaintiff, including the right to collect the current balance. See LVNV1-78. As shown in the documents attached hereto, Those documents show that the Account was originated by Cross River Bank for the benefit and use of Defendant. See LVNV1-47. Defendant did not make the necessary or minimum payments on the Account, leaving an outstanding balance as alleged in the

Complaint. Plaintiff is the current owner of the Account. As shown in LVNV47-78, Plaintiff acquired all ownership rights in the Account, including the right to collect the current balance alleged in the Complaint, plus any other relief the court awards. See the documents produced here and labeled LVNV1-78. Those documents are incorporated herein by reference pursuant to Civ. R. 33(C).

INTERROGATORY NO. 29: For all of the documents that you produced, identify the particular request to which the document is responsive.

RESPONSE: See responses to prior interrogatories.

INTERROGATORY NO. 30: For each and every response by Plaintiff to Defendant's First Request for Admissions that is other than an unqualified admission:

(a) Identify the number of each Request for Admission for which a response other than an unqualified admission is given;

RESPONSE: Objection. This request exceeds the forty (40) Interrogatory limit. Without waiving objections, see responses to Requests for Admissions, incorporated herein.

(b) Explain the specific grounds and describe with particularity all supporting facts on which Plaintiff relies to support each such denial, qualification, or other refusal to admit.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request exceeds the forty (40) Interrogatory limit. Without waiving objections, Plaintiff is not a debt collector. Plaintiff is a passive holding entity. Plaintiff did not communicate with Defendant. According to the business records, the Account was originated by Cross River Bank for the benefit and use of

Defendant. See LVNV1-47. Defendant did not make the necessary or minimum payments on the Account, leaving an outstanding balance as alleged in the Complaint. Plaintiff is the current owner of the Account. As shown in LVNV47-78, Plaintiff acquired all ownership rights in the Account, including the right to collect the current balance alleged in the Complaint, plus any other relief the court awards. See the documents produced here and labeled LVNV1-78. Those documents are incorporated herein by reference pursuant to Civ. R. 33(C).

INTERROGATORY NO. 31: Identify all documents of the “File No. 23-120249”, identify the Custodian of the documents, and for any document that the claim of privilege is asserted produce a privilege log.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request exceeds the forty (40) Interrogatory limit. Without waiving objections, no such documents are in Plaintiff’s possession.

INTERROGATORY NO. 33: Identify all servicers, service providers, attorneys, independent contractors, employees, contractors or otherwise agents of Plaintiff’s who have worked on/ reviewed documents of/or serviced the Account for the Plaintiff.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request exceeds the forty (40) Interrogatory limit. Plaintiff further objects to this request on the ground that it is irrelevant, immaterial, and is not reasonably calculated to lead to the discovery of admissible evidence. The amount paid by an assignee for an otherwise enforceable debt is legally irrelevant.

As to Objections,

/s/Boyd W. Gentry
Boyd W. Gentry (OH#0071057)

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ohio@stengerlaw.com

CERTIFICATE OF SERVICE

I certify that a copy of the foregoing has been sent by email to Andrew Barnes on July 17, 2024, at the following address: abarnes@abarneslaw.com

/s/Boyd W. Gentry
Boyd W. Gentry (OH#0071057)

Loan Agreement

Eric Wiseman

aea4de27-8d2d-47c3-9f6a-ad8f011928fb

Cross River Bank

Best Egg Loan Agreement and Promissory Note

The terms and conditions of this Loan Agreement and Promissory Note (this "Agreement") are a binding contract between Cross River Bank ("we," "us," or "our") and the borrower ("you" and "your"), whose name and address are listed above. The terms of this Agreement affect your rights and you should read them carefully and print a copy for your records. Your agreement to these terms means you agree to borrow and repay the money if your loan is approved under the terms of this Agreement, and agree to have any dispute with us resolved by binding arbitration to extent permitted by law.

1. Loan Terms.

- a. The principal Amount of Your Loan is: \$20,000.00
- b. The Origination Fee is: \$998.00
- c. The Amount Given to You Directly is: \$19,002.00
- d. The Interest Rate is: 27.25%.
- e. Your Payment Schedule is: 59 consecutive monthly payments of \$613.70 and one final payment of the unpaid principal balance, all unpaid interest, and all unpaid fees and charges. The first payment will be approximately one calendar month after the loan is funded. See paragraph 7. Payments, below, for more details.
- f. Your loan is unsecured.

2. Credit Reports. You hereby authorize us (and our service providers) to obtain consumer reports (also called credit reports) and related information about you from one or more consumer reporting agencies. We may also obtain additional consumer reports at any time in connection with the origination, servicing, administration, collection, or enforcement of the loan.

3. Verification of Information. We may verify any information you submit by requiring you to produce appropriate documentation or other proof, and also reserve the right to conduct such verification through third parties. You hereby authorize us to request and obtain data from any third parties to verify any information you provide to us in connection with your application. Verification of information may cause a delay in the disbursement of loan proceeds. We may terminate consideration of your application at any time in our sole discretion.

4. Loan Funding and Closing.

- **Funding.** Loan proceeds are disbursed as a deposit to your designated bank account and/or as a direct payment to the creditor(s) you designated, if any, pursuant to participating in Best Egg's Direct Pay program. You authorize us to disburse the loan proceeds by Automated Clearing House ("ACH") transfer to your designated account or on your behalf to your selected designee, including the creditor designated as set forth above.

- **Closing.** BY ELECTRONICALLY SIGNING OR AGREEING TO THIS AGREEMENT IN ANOTHER WAY, YOU ARE COMMITTING TO OBTAIN A LOAN FROM US IN THE AMOUNT AND ON THE TERMS SET FORTH IN THIS AGREEMENT. YOU GENERALLY HAVE NO RIGHT TO RESCIND THE LOAN ONCE MADE BUT YOU MAY PREPAY THE LOAN AT ANY TIME WITHOUT PENALTY. WE HAVE NOT AGREED TO MAKE A LOAN TO YOU UNLESS AND UNTIL WE INFORM YOU THAT WE HAVE APPROVED YOUR LOAN APPLICATION.

5. Promise to Pay. You promise to pay to us the Amount of Your Loan set forth in paragraph 1, above, together with interest and fees as provided in this Agreement.

6. Interest. You agree to pay interest on the unpaid principal balance of the Amount of Your Loan from the date the loan proceeds are disbursed until the loan is paid in full, at the fixed annual Loan Interest Rate set forth in paragraph 1, above. Interest is calculated on a daily basis, on the unpaid principal balance, at the interest rate, and for the number of days that balance was unpaid. This is a simple interest obligation, and interest is not charged on unpaid interest. The Total Payments and amount of the Finance Charge set forth in the Truth in Lending Disclosure Statement assume that each payment is made on its due date. Late payments will result in more interest (and fees as set out in paragraph 12); early payments will result in less interest.

7. Payments. You agree to make monthly payments of principal and interest in the amounts set forth in the payment schedule in paragraph 1, above. The last payment may be a different amount because of rounding and because of when you made your prior payments and whether you paid them in full.

8. Making Your Loan Payments. If you authorize us and our successors and assigns (and any of our successors' and assigns' affiliates, agents or service providers) and in consideration of our disbursement of loan proceeds to you or your designee, including any creditor you designated pursuant to Best Egg's Direct Pay program, more rapidly by ACH than by check, we will automatically withdraw via debit from your designated account by ACH transfer the amount of each payment due on its due date as further described below. With regard to payments made by automatic withdrawal, you have the right to stop payment of automatic withdrawals or revoke your prior authorization for automatic withdrawals by notifying us or your financial institution at least three (3) banking days before the scheduled date of transfer. You may elect at any time to make payments by check or another method by contacting our customer service department at 844-825-2608. If you do not provide authorization to debit your designated account by ACH transfer, then you will be deemed to have elected to pay by another method in accordance with the foregoing provisions.

If you elect to make payments by ACH transfer, you authorize us and our successors and assigns (and any of our successors' and assigns' affiliates, agents or service providers) to debit your designated account by ACH transfer for the amount of each remaining payment due on its due date. However, if your payment due date occurs on a non-business day, your account will be debited the next business day. You will maintain sufficient funds in your designated account to make these payments. This authorization does not affect your obligation to pay when due all amounts payable on your loan, whether or not there are sufficient funds in your accounts. The foregoing authorization is in addition to, and not in limitation of, any rights of setoff we may have. You have the right to have any unauthorized debit credited to your bank account in accordance with the applicable provisions of the Electronic Funds Transfer Act as implemented

by Federal Reserve System Regulation E. If you stop the automatic withdrawals, you are still obligated to make each payment that is due. You will receive a monthly statement advising of your payment amount.

If you elect to make payments by check or any method other than automatic withdrawal by ACH transfer, you must send such payments as directed on your monthly billing statements. We do not accept payments in cash or by credit card or gift card. You may also contact us for instructions on how to make payments by other payment options.

9. Prepayments and Partial Payments. You may make any payment early, in whole or in part, without penalty or premium at any time. Any partial prepayment is to be applied to any applicable payment or returned payment fees, interest, and then to the principal, and does not postpone the due date of any subsequent monthly installments, unless we otherwise agree in writing. If you prepay in part, you agree to continue to make regularly scheduled payments until all amounts due under this Agreement are paid. **We may accept late payments or partial payments, even though marked "paid in full" or with similar language, without losing any rights under this Agreement.** We will use any payment we receive to pay any payment then due, in whole or in part. If no payment is then due, we will use any payment of the regularly scheduled payment amount to pay the next scheduled payment. If the next scheduled payment has been paid, or if the payment is in another amount, we will treat the payment as a partial prepayment, unless you and we agree otherwise.

10. Application of Payments. All regularly scheduled payments are to be applied first to any applicable payment or returned payment fees, interest, and then to the principal, and then to collection and other permitted expenses provided; however, that after an Event of Default (as defined below), payments will be applied to your obligations as we determine in our sole discretion.

11. Other Borrower Obligations. You agree that you (A) are a US citizen or permanent resident and (B) did not and will not, in connection with your loan application: (i) make any false, misleading or deceptive statements or omissions of fact in your application; (ii) misrepresent your identity, or describe, present or portray yourself as a person other than yourself; or (iii) use any of the loan proceeds to fund any post-secondary educational expenses, including, but not limited to, tuition, fees, books, supplies, miscellaneous expenses, or room and board. You acknowledge and agree that we may rely without independent verification on the accuracy, authenticity, and completeness of all information you provide to us. You certify that the proceeds of the loan will not be used for the purpose of purchasing or carrying any securities or to fund any illegal activity.

12. Fees.

- **Origination Fee.** If applicable, you agree to pay a non-refundable Origination Fee to us, as set forth in paragraph 1. Loan Terms, above. This fee will be deducted from your loan proceeds, so the Amount Given to You Directly or on your behalf may be less than the full principal Amount of Your Loan. You acknowledge that the Origination Fee will be considered part of the principal on your loan and is subject to the accrual of interest.
- **Returned Check or ACH Fee.** You agree to pay a fee of \$15 if ACH transfers or checks are returned or fail due to insufficient funds in your account or for any other reason. The bank that holds your designated account may assess its own fee in addition to the fee we assess.

- **Late Fee.** If your payment is not received by us within three days of the due date, we will charge a late fee in the amount of \$15. We will charge only one late fee on each late payment. These fees may be collected using ACH transfers initiated by us from your designated account. Any such late fee assessed is immediately due and payable (subject to application of payments in paragraph 10). Any payment received after 6:00 P.M., Eastern Time, on a banking day is deemed received on the next succeeding banking day.

13. Default. You may be deemed in default on your loan (each, an "Event of Default") if you: (1) fail to pay timely any amount due on your loan; (2) file or have instituted against you any bankruptcy or insolvency proceedings or make any assignment for the benefit of creditors; (3) die; (4) commit fraud or make any material misrepresentation in this Agreement, or any other documents, applications or related materials delivered to us in connection with your loan; or (5) fail to abide by the terms of this Agreement. Upon the occurrence of an Event of Default, and after any notice and opportunity to cure the default, if such notice and right to cure is required by applicable law, we may exercise all remedies available to us under applicable law and this Agreement including, without limitation, demand that you or your estate immediately pay all amounts owed on your loan.

14. Collection & Reporting of Delinquent Loans. You agree to pay all costs of collecting any delinquent payments, as permitted by applicable law, including, if we file suit in court, reasonable attorneys' fees for an attorney who is not our salaried employee. We may report information about your account to credit bureaus. Late payments, missed payments, or other defaults on your account may be reflected in your credit report.

15. Communications Consent: You agree that we and any of our affiliates, agents, service providers or assigns (and any of our assigns' affiliates, agents or service providers) may call you, leave you a voice prerecorded, or artificial voice message, or send a text, e-mail, or other electronic message to you for any purpose related to the processing, servicing and collection of your loan, for surveys or research or for any other informational purpose related to your loan (each a "Communication") using an automatic telephone dialing system or otherwise. You agree that we and any of our affiliates, agents, service providers or assigns (and any of our assigns' affiliates, agents or service providers) may call or text you at any telephone number associated with your loan, including cellular telephone numbers, and may send an e-mail to any email address associated with your loan. You also agree that we and any of our affiliates, agents, service providers or assigns (and any of our assigns' affiliates, agents or service providers) may include your personal information in a Communication and may conduct a Communication using an automatic telephone dialing system. We will not charge you for a Communication, but your data service provider may. In addition, you understand and agree that we and any of our affiliates, agents, service providers or assigns (and any of our assigns' affiliates, agents or service providers) may always communicate with you in any manner permissible by law that does not require your prior consent.

16. Assignment of Your Loan. You agree that we may, without further prior notice to or consent from you, assign any or all of our right, title and interest in this Agreement and your loan, including record of this loan, the debt incurred, any transfer of the obligation and your promise to repay, to anyone. Marlette Funding, LLC or its agents or designees, acting solely for this purpose as your agent, shall maintain at one of its offices in Wilmington, Delaware a copy of each assignment delivered to it and a register for the recordation of the name and address of the holder of your loan (including any assign, if any, who becomes the holder of your loan

pursuant to an assignment), and principal amounts (and stated interest) of your loan or loans owing to, such holder pursuant to the terms hereof from time to time (the "Register"). The entries in the Register shall be conclusive absent manifest error, and you, Cross River Bank or its agents or designees, and the holder of your loan (including any assign, if any, who becomes the holder of your loan pursuant to an assignment) shall treat the person whose name is recorded in the Register pursuant to the terms hereof as a holder of your loan hereunder for all purposes of this Agreement. Recordation in the Register is the sole means of assignment or transfer of the holder's (or its assign's) interest in your loan. The Register shall be available for inspection by you and any holder (including assigns), at any reasonable time and from time to time upon reasonable prior notice.

17. Entire Agreement. This Agreement represents the entire agreement between you and us regarding the subject matter hereof and supersedes all prior or contemporaneous communications, promises and proposals, whether oral, written or electronic, between us with respect to your application and loan.

18. Electronic Transactions. THIS AGREEMENT IS FULLY SUBJECT TO YOUR CONSENT TO ELECTRONIC TRANSACTIONS AND DISCLOSURES, WHICH YOU AGREED TO AT THE TIME OF YOUR APPLICATION. YOU EXPRESSLY AGREE THAT THIS AGREEMENT IS A "TRANSFERABLE RECORD" FOR ALL PURPOSES UNDER THE ELECTRONIC SIGNATURES IN GLOBAL AND NATIONAL COMMERCE ACT AND THE UNIFORM ELECTRONIC TRANSACTIONS ACT.

19. Notices. All notices and other communications to you hereunder may be given by email to your email address on file with us or by regular mail to your address on file with us, and shall be deemed to have been duly given and effective upon transmission. You acknowledge that you have sole access to the email account on file and that communications from us may contain sensitive, confidential, and collections-related communications. If your email address changes, you must notify us of the change. You also agree to update your residence address and telephone number if they change. You may send written correspondence to us at the following address: Best Egg, P.O. Box 42912, Philadelphia, PA 19101. You may also reach us by phone by dialing 844-825-2608 during normal business hours.

20. NO WARRANTIES. EXCEPT AS EXPRESSLY SET FORTH IN THIS AGREEMENT, WE MAKE NO REPRESENTATIONS OR WARRANTIES TO YOU, INCLUDING, BUT NOT LIMITED TO, ANY IMPLIED WARRANTIES OF MERCHANTABILITY OR FITNESS FOR A PARTICULAR PURPOSE.

21. LIMITATION ON LIABILITY. IN NO EVENT SHALL WE BE LIABLE TO YOU FOR ANY LOST PROFITS OR SPECIAL, EXEMPLARY, CONSEQUENTIAL OR PUNITIVE DAMAGES, EVEN IF INFORMED OF THE POSSIBILITY OF SUCH DAMAGES. FURTHERMORE, WE MAKE NO REPRESENTATION OR WARRANTY TO YOU REGARDING THE EFFECT THAT THE AGREEMENT MAY HAVE UPON YOUR FOREIGN, FEDERAL, STATE OR LOCAL TAX LIABILITY.

22. Waiver of Demand. You hereby waive demand, notice of non-payment, protest, and all other notices or demands whatsoever, unless such waiver is prohibited by law.

23. Amendments. Any changes to this Agreement must be in writing signed by you and us.

24. Miscellaneous. The parties acknowledge that there are no third party beneficiaries to this Agreement. You may not assign, transfer, sublicense or otherwise delegate your rights or obligations under this Agreement to another person without our prior written consent. Any such assignment, transfer, sublicense or delegation in violation of this paragraph 24 shall be null and void. We are located in the State of New Jersey and this Agreement will be entered into in the State of New Jersey. The provisions of this Agreement will be governed by federal laws and, to the extent that state law applies and is not preempted by federal law, the laws of the State of New Jersey, without regard to any principle of conflicts of laws that would require or permit the application of the laws of any other jurisdiction. Any waiver of a breach of any provision of this Agreement will not be deemed a waiver of any other subsequent breach. Failure or delay by either party to enforce any term or condition of this Agreement will not constitute a waiver of such term or condition. If at any time after the date of this Agreement, any of the provisions of this Agreement shall be held by any court of competent jurisdiction to be illegal, void or unenforceable, such provision shall be of no force and effect, but the illegality and unenforceability of such provision shall have no effect upon and shall not impair the enforceability of any other provisions of this Agreement. The headings in this Agreement are for reference purposes only and shall not affect the interpretation of this Agreement in any way. **Special Note for Residents of Colorado:** If you are a resident of the State of Colorado as of the date of this Agreement and the Annual Percentage Rate of your Loan as set forth in your Truth in Lending Disclosure Statement exceeds the maximum finance charge permitted for a "supervised loan" under C.R.S. § 5-2-201(2) then the provisions of this Agreement are governed by Colorado law except for terms preempted or authorized by federal law (including the interest rate, origination fee, late fee and returned check fee), which are governed by federal law and New Jersey law.

25. NOTICE TO ACTIVE DUTY MILITARY SERVICEMEMBERS AND THEIR DEPENDENTS:

Federal law provides important protections to members of the Armed Forces and their dependents relating to extensions of consumer credit. In general, the cost of consumer credit to a member of the Armed Forces and his or her dependent may not exceed an annual percentage rate of 36 percent. This rate must include, as applicable to the credit transaction or account: The costs associated with credit insurance premiums; fees for ancillary products sold in connection with the credit transaction; any application fee charged (other than certain application fees for specified credit transactions or accounts); and any participation fee charged (other than certain participation fees for a credit card account).

For more information regarding your rights as a covered borrower under the Military Lending Act, please call 844-876-2611.

26. Arbitration.

- a. Either party to this Agreement, or any subsequent assign of this Agreement, may, at its sole election, require that the sole and exclusive forum and remedy for resolution of a Claim be final and binding arbitration pursuant to this paragraph 26 (the "Arbitration Provision"), unless you opt out as provided in paragraph 26(b) below. As used in this Arbitration Provision, "Claim" shall include any past, present, or future claim, dispute, or controversy involving you (or persons claiming through or connected with you), on the one hand, and us and/or any assign (or persons claiming through or connected with us and/or any assign), on the other hand, relating to or arising out of this Agreement and/or the activities or relationships that involve, lead to, or result from this Agreement,

including (except to the extent provided otherwise in the last sentence of paragraph 26(f) below) the validity or enforceability of this Arbitration Provision, any part thereof, or the entire Agreement. Claims are subject to arbitration regardless of whether they arise from contract; tort (intentional or otherwise); a constitution, statute, common law, or principles of equity; or otherwise. Claims include matters arising as initial claims, counter-claims, cross-claims, third-party claims, or otherwise. The scope of this Arbitration Provision is to be given the broadest possible interpretation that is enforceable.

- b. You may opt out of this Arbitration Provision for all purposes by sending an arbitration opt-out notice to Best Egg, P.O. Box 42912, Philadelphia, PA 19101, only if received at the specified address within 30 days of the date of your electronic acceptance of the terms of this Agreement. The opt-out notice must clearly state that you are rejecting arbitration; identify the Agreement to which it applies by date; provide your name, address, and social security number; and be signed by you. You may send the opt-out notice in any manner you see fit as long as it is received at the specified address within the specified time. No other methods can be used to opt-out of this Arbitration Provision. If the opt-out notice is sent on your behalf by a third party, such third party must include evidence of his or her authority to submit the opt out notice on your behalf.
- c. The party initiating arbitration shall do so with the American Arbitration Association (the "AAA") or JAMS. The arbitration shall be conducted according to, and the location of the arbitration shall be determined in accordance with, the rules and policies of the administrator selected, except to the extent the rules conflict with this Arbitration Provision or any countervailing law. In the case of a conflict between the rules and policies of the administrator and this Arbitration Provision, this Arbitration Provision shall control, subject to countervailing law, unless all parties to the arbitration consent to have the rules and policies of the administrator apply.
- d. If we (or any assign) elect arbitration, we (or the assign, as the case may be) shall pay all the administrator's filing costs and administrative fees (other than hearing fees). If you elect arbitration, filing costs and administrative fees (other than hearing fees) shall be paid in accordance with the rules of the administrator selected, or in accordance with countervailing law if contrary to the administrator's rules. We (or the assign, as the case may be) shall pay the administrator's hearing fees for one full day of arbitration hearings. Fees for hearings that exceed one day will be paid by the party requesting the hearing, unless the administrator's rules or applicable law require otherwise, or you request that we (or the assign) pay them and we agree (or the assign agrees) to do so. Each party shall bear the expense of its own attorneys' fees, except as otherwise provided by law. If a statute gives you the right to recover any of these fees, these statutory rights shall apply in the arbitration notwithstanding anything to the contrary herein.
- e. Within 30 days of a final award by the arbitrator, any party may appeal the award for reconsideration by a three-arbitrator panel selected according to the rules of the arbitrator administrator. In the event of such an appeal, any opposing party may cross-appeal within 30 days after notice of the appeal. The panel will reconsider de novo all aspects of the initial award that are appealed. Costs and conduct of any appeal shall be governed by this Arbitration Provision and the administrator's rules, in the same way as the initial arbitration proceeding. Any award by the individual arbitrator that is not subject to appeal, and any panel award on appeal, shall be final and binding, except for any appeal right under the Federal Arbitration Act ("FAA"), and may be entered as a judgment in any court of competent jurisdiction.
- f. We agree not to invoke our right to arbitrate an individual Claim you may bring in Small Claims Court or an equivalent court, if any, so long as the Claim is pending only in that court. **NO ARBITRATION SHALL PROCEED ON A CLASS, REPRESENTATIVE, OR COLLECTIVE BASIS (INCLUDING AS PRIVATE ATTORNEY GENERAL ON BEHALF**

OF OTHERS), EVEN IF THE CLAIM OR CLAIMS THAT ARE THE SUBJECT OF THE ARBITRATION HAD PREVIOUSLY BEEN ASSERTED (OR COULD HAVE BEEN ASSERTED) IN A COURT AS CLASS REPRESENTATIVE, OR COLLECTIVE ACTIONS IN A COURT. Unless consented to in writing by all parties to the arbitration, no party to the arbitration may join, consolidate, or otherwise bring claims for or on behalf of two or more individuals or unrelated corporate entities in the same arbitration unless those persons are parties to a single transaction. Unless consented to in writing by all parties to the arbitration, an award in arbitration shall determine the rights and obligations of the named parties only, and only with respect to the claims in arbitration, and shall not (a) determine the rights, obligations, or interests of anyone other than a named party, or resolve any Claim of anyone other than a named party; nor (b) make an award for the benefit of, or against, anyone other than a named party. No administrator or arbitrator shall have the power or authority to waive, modify, or fail to enforce this paragraph 26(f), and any attempt to do so, whether by rule, policy, arbitration decision or otherwise, shall be invalid and unenforceable. Any challenge to the validity of this paragraph 26(f) shall be determined exclusively by a court and not by the administrator or any arbitrator.

- g. This Arbitration Provision is made pursuant to a transaction involving interstate commerce and shall be governed by and enforceable under the FAA. The arbitrator will apply substantive law consistent with the FAA and applicable statutes of limitations. The arbitrator may award damages or other types of relief permitted by applicable substantive law, subject to the limitations set forth in this Arbitration Provision. The arbitrator will not be bound by judicial rules of procedure and evidence that would apply in a court. The arbitrator shall take steps to reasonably protect confidential information.
- h. This Arbitration Provision shall survive (i) suspension, termination, revocation, closure, or amendments to this Agreement and the relationship of the parties and/or assignee; (ii) the bankruptcy or insolvency of any party or other person; and (iii) any transfer of any loan or this Agreement to any other person or entity. If any portion of this Arbitration Provision other than paragraph 26(f) is deemed invalid or unenforceable, the remaining portions of this Arbitration Provision shall nevertheless remain valid and in force. If an arbitration is brought on a class, representative, or collective basis, and the limitations on such proceedings in paragraph 26(f) are finally adjudicated pursuant to the last sentence of paragraph 26(f) to be unenforceable, then no arbitration shall be had. In no event shall any invalidation be deemed to authorize an arbitrator to determine Claims or make awards beyond those authorized in this Arbitration Provision. THE PARTIES ACKNOWLEDGE THAT THEY HAVE A RIGHT TO LITIGATE CLAIMS THROUGH A COURT BEFORE A JUDGE OR JURY, BUT WILL NOT HAVE THAT RIGHT IF ANY PARTY ELECTS ARBITRATION PURSUANT TO THIS ARBITRATION PROVISION. THE PARTIES HEREBY KNOWINGLY AND VOLUNTARILY WAIVE THEIR RIGHTS TO LITIGATE SUCH CLAIMS IN A COURT BEFORE A JUDGE OR JURY UPON ELECTION OF ARBITRATION BY ANY PARTY.
- i. EXCEPTION: Active duty military servicemembers and their dependents are exempt from arbitration to the extent provided for in the Military Lending Act.

NOTICE TO CONSUMER:

- 1. Do not sign this Agreement before you read it.**
- 2. You are entitled to a copy of this Agreement.**
- 3. You may prepay the unpaid balance at any time without penalty.**

IMPORTANT: READ BEFORE SIGNING. The terms of this agreement should be read carefully because only those terms in writing are enforceable. No other terms or oral promises not contained in this written contract may be legally enforced. You may change the terms of this Agreement only by another written agreement. **IT IS IMPORTANT THAT YOU THOROUGHLY READ THE CONTRACT BEFORE YOU SIGN IT.**

Signature: Eric Wiseman, Signature Date: 8/25/2021
IP Address: 99.55.155.230

You can contact us for purposes of this Agreement at Best Egg, P.O. Box 42912, Philadelphia, PA 19101. For customer service, our telephone number is 844-825-2608.

STATE LAW NOTICES:

ALL BORROWERS: Oral agreements or commitments to loan money, extend credit, or to forbear from enforcing repayment of a debt, are not enforceable. To protect you and us from misunderstanding or disappointment, any agreements we reach covering such matters are contained in this writing, which is the complete and exclusive statement of the agreement between us, except as we later may agree in writing to modify.

CALIFORNIA RESIDENTS: A married applicant may apply for a separate account. If we take any adverse action as defined by § 1785.3 of the California Civil Code and the adverse action is based, in whole or in part, on any information contained in a consumer credit report, you have the right to obtain within 60 days a free copy of your consumer credit report from the consumer reporting agency who furnished the consumer credit report and from any other consumer credit reporting agency that complies and maintains files on consumers on a nationwide basis.

CALIFORNIA and UTAH RESIDENTS: As required by California and Utah law, you are hereby notified that a negative credit report reflecting on your credit record may be submitted to a credit reporting agency if you fail to fulfill the terms of your credit obligations.

KANSAS (and IOWA residents if the principal amount of this loan exceeds \$20,000): Important: read before signing. The terms of this agreement should be read carefully because only those terms in writing are enforceable. No other terms or oral promises not contained in this written contract may be legally enforced. We may change the terms of this agreement only by another written agreement.

MARYLAND RESIDENTS: To the extent that any court determines that this Agreement is subject to Maryland law concerning consumer credit, you and we agree and elect to make this loan pursuant to Subtitle 10 (Credit Grantor Closed End Credit provisions) of Title 12 of the Maryland Commercial Law Article only to the extent that such provisions are not inconsistent with our authority under federal law (12 U.S.C. § 1831d) and related regulations and interpretations, which authority we expressly reserve.

MASSACHUSETTS RESIDENTS: Massachusetts law prohibits discrimination based upon marital status or sexual orientation.

MISSOURI AND NEBRASKA RESIDENTS: Oral loan agreements or commitments to loan money, extend credit or to forbear from enforcing repayment of such debt, including promises to extend or renew such debt, are not enforceable. To protect you and us and any holder of this

agreement from misunderstanding or disappointment, any agreements we reach covering such matters are contained in this writing, which is the complete and exclusive statement of the agreement between us, except as we may later agree in writing to modify it.

NEW HAMPSHIRE RESIDENTS: You are not required to sign this agreement (directly or indirectly), or agree to enter into such an agreement as a condition of purchasing any property, goods or services. Reasonable attorney fees shall be awarded to the prevailing party in any action you bring against us or we bring against you. If we successfully assert a partial defense or set-off, recoupment, or counterclaim to an action brought by you, the court may withhold from you the entire amount or such portion of the attorney's fees as the court considers equitable.

NEW JERSEY RESIDENTS: The paragraph headings of this Agreement are a table of contents and not contract terms. Portions of this Agreement with references to actions taken to the extent of applicable law apply to acts or practices that New Jersey law permits or requires. In this Agreement, actions or practices (i) which are or may be permitted by "applicable law" are permitted by New Jersey law, and (ii) that may be or will be taken by us unless prohibited by "applicable law" are permitted by New Jersey law.

NEW YORK, RHODE ISLAND and VERMONT RESIDENTS: You understand and agree that we may obtain a consumer credit report in connection with this application and in connection with any update, renewals for extension of any credit as a result of this application. If you ask, you will be informed whether or not such a report was obtained, and if so, the name and address of the agency that furnished the report. You also understand and agree that Lender may obtain a consumer credit report in connection with the review or collection of any loan made to you as a result of this application or for other legitimate purposes related to such loans.

NORTH DAKOTA RESIDENTS ONLY: Notice: Money brokers are licensed and regulated by the Department of Financial Institutions, 2000 Schafer Street, Suite G, Bismarck, North Dakota 58501-1204. The Department of Financial Institutions has not passed on the merits of the contract and licensing does not constitute an approval of the terms or of the broker's ability to arrange any loan. Complaints regarding the services of money brokers should be directed to the Department of Financial Institutions. (NDAC 13-05-01-09)

OHIO RESIDENTS: The Ohio laws against discrimination require that all creditors make credit equally available to all creditworthy customers, and that credit reporting agencies maintain separate credit histories on each individual upon request. The Ohio Civil Rights Commission administers compliance with the law.

SOUTH DAKOTA RESIDENTS: Any improprieties in making the loan or in loan practices may be referred to the South Dakota Division of Banking, located at 1601 N. Harrison Avenue, Suite 1, Pierre, SD 57501, or by phone at 605.773.3421.

WISCONSIN RESIDENTS: For married Wisconsin residents, your signature confirms that this loan obligation is being incurred in the interest of your marriage or family. No provision of any marital property agreement (pre-marital agreement), unilateral statement under § 766.59 of the Wisconsin statutes or court decree under § 766.70 adversely affects our interest unless, prior to the time that the loan is approved, we are furnished with a copy of the marital property agreement, statement, or decree or have actual knowledge of the adverse provision. If this loan for which you are applying is granted, you will notify us if you have a spouse who needs to receive notification that credit has been extended to you.

DATE: 8/26/2021

TRUTH IN LENDING DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

Lender

Cross River Bank
885 Teaneck Road
Teaneck, NJ 07666

Borrower

Eric Wiseman

ANNUAL PERCENTAGE RATE	FINANCE CHARGE	Amount Financed	Total of Payments
The cost of your credit at a yearly rate	The dollar amount the credit will cost you	The amount of credit provided to you or on your behalf	The amount you will have paid after you have made all payments as scheduled
29.91%	\$17,823.89	\$19,002.00	\$36,825.89

Your payment schedule will be as follows:

Number of Payments	Amounts	When payments are due
59	\$613.70	First payment is due on 9/25/2021, and then monthly on the same date thereafter.
1	\$617.59	

Late charges: If your payment arrives after your 3-day grace period, you will be charged a late fee in the amount of \$15. This fee is charged only once per late payment.

Prepayment policy: If you pay off your loan in advance, you will not be charged a penalty. In the event of a prepayment, you will not be entitled to a refund of any pre-paid finance charges or other fees.

See your Loan Agreement for any additional information about nonpayment, default or other matters related to your loan.

Itemization of amount financed:

Amount of Your Loan: \$20,000.00

Origination Fee: \$998.00

Amount Given to You Directly or your designee: \$19,002.00

Annual Loan Interest Rate: 27.25%. Interest at this Loan Interest Rate plus the Origination Fee results in the Finance Charge and Annual Percentage Rate disclosed above.

LVNV13

Eric Wiseman

Account Number:

0074

Statement Date:

August 28, 2021

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

855-282-6353
CUSTOMER SERVICE PHONE NUMBER AND EASTERN HOURS: Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm
 Friday 8am-8pm
 Saturday 9am-1pm

SEND PAYMENT ONLY TO THIS ADDRESS: Best Egg
 P O Box 207865
 Dallas, TX 75320-7865

SEND ALL OTHER CORRESPONDENCE TO THIS ADDRESS: Best Egg
 P O Box 42912
 Philadelphia, PA 19101

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT

TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: **\$613.70**

PAYMENT DUE BY: **September 25, 2021**

Scheduled Payment:	\$613.70	Late Charges:	\$0.00
Past Due Payments:	\$0.00	Other Fees:	\$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received:	
Last Payment Amount:	\$0.00

Current Balance*
\$20,000.00

APPLIED TO:

Principal:	\$0.00	Interest:	\$0.00
Late Fees:	\$0.00	Other:	\$0.00

Total Interest Paid:
\$0.00

Thanks for being a Best Egg customer!

Our Payment Address has changed!

Mail in your payments to:

Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

And...you asked, we listened!

You can now log in anytime to **BestEgg.com** to make payments, view your account information, see a breakdown of your loan, and more!

Tear along this handy-dandy perforated edge

*This is not the payoff amount.

See Reverse Side For Important Information.

107007-126189-MPMS-72

PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman

Total Due: **\$613.70**

Account Number:

Due Date: **September 25, 2021**

44140074

Please do NOT send cash

- ✓ Make checks payable to "Best Egg"
- ✓ Write your account number on your check
- ✓ Mail 5-7 days ahead for on-time delivery

Best Egg
PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

Put a checkmark in this box if you need to update your address or phone number on the back of this coupon.

0074 0000061370 6

Payment Options

Pay Automatically: Sign up for automatic payments today! Your monthly payment will be deducted from your bank account and post on your due date.

Online: Log in anytime to BestEgg.com to make, schedule or cancel a payment. Please note that all payments received after 7pm ET won't post to your account until the next business day.

Phone: Call us at 855-282-6353 to make a one-time payment.

Mail: Mail us a check to the address below. Please include your Best Egg Account Number in the Memo Line and allow 5-7 business days for your payment to reach us.

Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

Overnight your payment: You can overnight your payment by including your Account Number on the Memo Line on your check to:

Lockbox Services 207865
Best Egg
2975 Regent Blvd
Ste 100
Irving, TX 75063

Best Egg may charge a \$7 processing fee for each payment to customers not enrolled in automatic payments.

General Information

Late Fees: To avoid \$15 late fees on your account, please make your payments on-time and of the minimum payment due.

Other Fees: Nonsufficient Funds Fees and Returned Payment Fees are applied to your account if a payment drafted cannot be completed because the account did not have sufficient funds, or if the payment was returned. To avoid a \$15 fee on your loan, please make sure there are enough funds in your bank account for your monthly payment.

Contact Us:

Email Us: Loan_assistance@mybestegg.com
Give us a call at 855-282-6353 during these hours:
Monday - Thursday 8:00am - 10:00pm ET
Friday 8:00am - 8:00pm ET
Saturday 9:00am - 1:00pm ET

Correspondence Address:

Best Egg
P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

Credit Bureau Reporting: We may report information about the status your Best Egg loan to credit bureaus. Late payments, missed payments or other delinquencies on your account may be reflected in your credit report.

Due Date Change: Many customers may be able to change their monthly due date. Give us a call at the number and hours listed

Let's connect on social media. We'd love to hear from you.

facebook.com/besteggloan

[@mybestegg](https://twitter.com/mybestegg)

ADDRESS/PHONE NUMBER UPDATE

Update your contact information on the lines below and be sure to check the box on the front of this coupon.

Updated Addresses:

RESIDENTIAL STREET ADDRESS _____

CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

BILLING STREET ADDRESS _____

CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

Updated Contact Information:

HOME PHONE: _____

BUSINESS PHONE: _____

EMAIL ADDRESS: _____

LVNV15

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: XXXXXXXXXX0074

Statement Date: **September 28, 2021**

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

**CUSTOMER SERVICE
PHONE NUMBER AND
EASTERN HOURS:** 855-282-6353
Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm
Friday 8am-8pm
Saturday 9am-1pm

**SEND PAYMENT ONLY
TO THIS ADDRESS:** Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

**SEND ALL OTHER
CORRESPONDENCE
TO THIS ADDRESS:** Best Egg
P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT

TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: **\$613.70**

PAYMENT DUE BY: **October 25, 2021**

Scheduled Payment:	\$613.70	Late Charges:	\$0.00
Past Due Payments:	\$0.00	Other Fees:	\$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received:	September 25, 2021
Last Payment Amount:	\$613.70

**Current
Balance***
\$19,834.25

APPLIED TO:

Principal:	\$165.75	Interest:	\$447.95	Total Interest Paid:	
Late Fees:	\$0.00	Other:	\$0.00	\$447.95	

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Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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See Reverse Side For Important Information.

✓ Tear along this handy-slanty perforated edge

*This is not the payoff amount.

107002-126199-MPMS-72

PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman
Account Number:
44140074

Total Due: **\$613.70**
Due Date: **October 25, 2021**

Please do NOT send cash

- ✓ Make checks payable to "Best Egg"
- ✓ Write your account number on your check
- ✓ Mail 5-7 days ahead for on-time delivery

Best Egg
PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

Put a checkmark in this box if you need to update your address or phone number on the back of this coupon.

XXXXXXXXXX0074 0000061370 6

Payment Options

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Online: Log in anytime to BestEgg.com to make, schedule or cancel a payment. Please note that all payments received after 7pm ET won't post to your account until the next business day.

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Mail: Mail us a check to the address below. Please include your Best Egg Account Number in the Memo Line and allow 5-7 business days for your payment to reach us.

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Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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Best Egg
2975 Regent Blvd
Ste 100
Irving, TX 75063

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Updated Addresses:

RESIDENTIAL STREET ADDRESS _____

CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

BILLING STREET ADDRESS _____

CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

Updated Contact Information:

HOME PHONE: _____

BUSINESS PHONE: _____

EMAIL ADDRESS: _____

LVNV17

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: [REDACTED] 0074

Statement Date: **October 28, 2021**

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

**CUSTOMER SERVICE
PHONE NUMBER AND
EASTERN HOURS:** 855-282-6353
Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm
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Saturday 9am-1pm

**SEND PAYMENT ONLY
TO THIS ADDRESS:** Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

**SEND ALL OTHER
CORRESPONDENCE
TO THIS ADDRESS:** Best Egg
P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT

TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: **\$613.70**

PAYMENT DUE BY: **November 25, 2021**

Scheduled Payment: \$613.70 Late Charges: \$0.00
Past Due Payments: \$0.00 Other Fees: \$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received: October 25, 2021
Last Payment Amount: \$613.70

**Current
Balance***

\$19,664.78

APPLIED TO:

Principal: \$169.47 Interest: \$444.23
Late Fees: \$0.00 Other: \$0.00

Total Interest Paid:
\$892.18

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Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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107002-126199-MRMS-72

PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman
Account Number:
44140074

Total Due: **\$613.70**
Due Date: **November 25, 2021**

Please do NOT send cash

- ✓ Make checks payable to "Best Egg"
- ✓ Write your account number on your check
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Best Egg
PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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[REDACTED] 0074 0000061370 6

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Contact Us:

Email Us: Loan_assistance@mybestegg.com
Give us a call at 855-282-6353 during these hours:
Monday - Thursday 8:00am - 10:00pm ET
Friday 8:00am - 8:00pm ET
Saturday 9:00am - 1:00pm ET

Correspondence Address:

Best Egg
P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

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facebook.com/besteggloan

[@mybestegg](https://twitter.com/mybestegg)

ADDRESS/PHONE NUMBER UPDATE

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Updated Addresses:

RESIDENTIAL STREET ADDRESS _____

CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

BILLING STREET ADDRESS _____

CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

Updated Contact Information:

HOME PHONE _____

BUSINESS PHONE _____

EMAIL ADDRESS _____

LVNV19

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: [REDACTED] 0074
Statement Date: **January 28, 2022**

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

855-282-6353
Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm
Friday 8am-8pm
Saturday 9am-1pm
SEND PAYMENT ONLY TO THIS ADDRESS:
Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865
SEND ALL OTHER CORRESPONDENCE TO THIS ADDRESS:
Best Egg
P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT

TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: \$613.70
PAYMENT DUE BY: February 25, 2022

Scheduled Payment: \$613.70 Late Charges: \$0.00
Past Due Payments: \$0.00 Other Fees: \$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received: January 25, 2022
Last Payment Amount: \$613.70

Current Balance*
\$19,163.05

APPLIED TO:

Principal: \$166.34 Interest: \$447.36
Late Fees: \$0.00 Other: \$0.00

Total Interest Paid:
\$2,231.55

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Our Payment Address has changed!

Mail in your payments to:

Best Egg
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*This is not the payoff amount.

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107002-126139-MPM5-72

PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman
Account Number:
44140074

Total Due: **\$613.70**
Due Date: **February 25, 2022**

Please do NOT send cash

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- ✓ Make checks payable to "Best Egg"
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Mail: Mail us a check to the address below. Please include your Best Egg Account Number in the Memo Line and allow 5-7 business days for your payment to reach us.

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Dallas, TX 75320-7865

Overnight your payment: You can overnight your payment by including your Account Number on the Memo Line on your check to:

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Best Egg
2975 Regent Blvd
Ste 100
Irving, TX 75063

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CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

Updated Contact Information:

HOME PHONE _____

BUSINESS PHONE _____

EMAIL ADDRESS _____

LVNV21

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: XXXXXXXXXX0074

Statement Date: **February 28, 2022**

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

**CUSTOMER SERVICE
PHONE NUMBER AND
EASTERN HOURS:** 855-282-6353
Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm
Friday 8am-8pm
Saturday 9am-1pm

**SEND PAYMENT ONLY
TO THIS ADDRESS:** Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

**SEND ALL OTHER
CORRESPONDENCE
TO THIS ADDRESS:** Best Egg
P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT

TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: **\$613.70**

PAYMENT DUE BY: **March 25, 2022**

Scheduled Payment: \$613.70 Late Charges: \$0.00
Past Due Payments: \$0.00 Other Fees: \$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received: February 25, 2022
Last Payment Amount: \$613.70

**Current
Balance***
\$18,992.86

APPLIED TO:

Principal: \$170.19 Interest: \$443.51
Late Fees: \$0.00 Other: \$0.00

Total Interest Paid:
\$2,675.06

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107002-126190-MPMS-72

PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman
Account Number:
44140074

Total Due: **\$613.70**
Due Date: **March 25, 2022**

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Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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Best Egg
2975 Regent Blvd
Ste 100
Irving, TX 75063

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CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

Updated Contact Information:

HOME PHONE: _____

BUSINESS PHONE: _____

EMAIL ADDRESS: _____

Eric Wiseman

Account Number:

0074

Statement Date:

March 28, 2022

CUSTOMER SERVICE
PHONE NUMBER AND
EASTERN HOURS:

855-282-6353

Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm
Friday 8am-8pm
Saturday 9am-1pmSEND PAYMENT ONLY
TO THIS ADDRESS:Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865SEND ALL OTHER
CORRESPONDENCE
TO THIS ADDRESS:Best Egg
P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751**BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT**TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: **\$613.70**PAYMENT DUE BY: **April 25, 2022**

Scheduled Payment:	\$613.70	Late Charges:	\$0.00
Past Due Payments:	\$0.00	Other Fees:	\$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received:	March 25, 2022
Last Payment Amount:	\$613.70

**Current
Balance*****\$18,776.19****APPLIED TO:**

Principal:	\$216.67	Interest:	\$397.03
Late Fees:	\$0.00	Other:	\$0.00

Total Interest Paid:
\$3,072.09

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107002-176199-MPMS-72

PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman

Total Due: **\$613.70**

Account Number:

Due Date: **April 25, 2022**

44140074

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Best Egg
2975 Regent Blvd
Ste 100
Irving, TX 75063

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CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

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HOME PHONE _____

BUSINESS PHONE _____

EMAIL ADDRESS _____

Eric Wiseman

Account Number:

10074

Statement Date:

April 28, 2022

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

855-282-6353
CUSTOMER SERVICE
PHONE NUMBER AND
EASTERN HOURS: Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm
 Friday 8am-8pm
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SEND PAYMENT ONLY
TO THIS ADDRESS: Best Egg
 P O Box 207865
 Dallas, TX 75320-7865

SEND ALL OTHER
CORRESPONDENCE
TO THIS ADDRESS: Best Egg
 P O Box 42912
 Philadelphia, PA 19101

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT
TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: \$613.70
PAYMENT DUE BY: May 25, 2022

Scheduled Payment:	\$613.70	Late Charges:	\$0.00
Past Due Payments:	\$0.00	Other Fees:	\$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received:	April 25, 2022
Last Payment Amount:	\$613.70

APPLIED TO:

Principal:	\$179.15	Interest:	\$434.55
Late Fees:	\$0.00	Other:	\$0.00

**Current
Balance***
\$18,597.04
**Total Interest Paid:
\$3,506.64**

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107002-125199-MPMS-72

PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman

Total Due: **\$613.70**

Account Number:

Due Date: **May 25, 2022**

44140074

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Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

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CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

Updated Contact Information:

HOME PHONE _____

BUSINESS PHONE _____

EMAIL ADDRESS: _____

LVNV27

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: [REDACTED] 0074

Statement Date: **May 28, 2022**

**CUSTOMER SERVICE
PHONE NUMBER AND
EASTERN HOURS:** 855-282-6353
Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm
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Saturday 9am-1pm

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TO THIS ADDRESS:** Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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CORRESPONDENCE
TO THIS ADDRESS:** Best Egg
P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT

TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: \$613.70

PAYMENT DUE BY: June 25, 2022

Scheduled Payment: \$613.70 Late Charges: \$0.00
Past Due Payments: \$0.00 Other Fees: \$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received: May 25, 2022
Last Payment Amount: \$613.70

APPLIED TO:

Principal: \$197.18 Interest: \$416.52
Late Fees: \$0.00 Other: \$0.00

**Current
Balance***
\$18,399.86

Total Interest Paid:
\$3,923.16

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107002-126199-MPMS-72

PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman

Account Number:
44140074

Total Due: **\$613.70**

Due Date: **June 25, 2022**

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CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

Updated Contact Information:

HOME PHONE _____

BUSINESS PHONE _____

EMAIL ADDRESS: _____

LVNV29

Eric Wiseman

Account Number:

0074

Statement Date:

June 28, 2022

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

CUSTOMER SERVICE PHONE NUMBER AND EASTERN HOURS:	855-282-6353 Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm Friday 8am-8pm Saturday 9am-1pm
SEND PAYMENT ONLY TO THIS ADDRESS:	Best Egg P O Box 207865 Dallas, TX 75320-7865
SEND ALL OTHER CORRESPONDENCE TO THIS ADDRESS:	Best Egg P O Box 42912 Philadelphia, PA 19101

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT

TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: **\$613.70**

PAYMENT DUE BY: **July 25, 2022**

Scheduled Payment:	\$613.70	Late Charges:	\$0.00
Past Due Payments:	\$0.00	Other Fees:	\$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received:	June 25, 2022
Last Payment Amount:	\$613.70

**Current
Balance***

APPLIED TO:

Principal:	\$187.86	Interest:	\$425.84
Late Fees:	\$0.00	Other:	\$0.00

\$18,212.00

Total Interest Paid:
\$4,349.00

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Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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107903-126199-MPMS-72

PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman
Account Number:
44140074

Total Due: **\$613.70**
Due Date: **July 25, 2022**

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P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

Credit Bureau Reporting: We may report information about the status your Best Egg loan to credit bureaus. Late payments, missed payments or other delinquencies on your account may be reflected in your credit report.

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[@mybestegg](https://twitter.com/mybestegg)

ADDRESS/PHONE NUMBER UPDATE

Update your contact information on the lines below and be sure to check the box on the front of this coupon.

Updated Addresses:

Updated Contact Information:

RESIDENTIAL STREET ADDRESS _____

BILLING STREET ADDRESS _____

HOME PHONE: _____

BUSINESS PHONE: _____

CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

EMAIL ADDRESS: _____

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: XXXXXXXXXX0074
Statement Date: **July 28, 2022**

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

855-282-6353
CUSTOMER SERVICE PHONE NUMBER AND EASTERN HOURS: Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm
Friday 8am-8pm
Saturday 9am-1pm
SEND PAYMENT ONLY TO THIS ADDRESS: Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865
SEND ALL OTHER CORRESPONDENCE TO THIS ADDRESS: Best Egg
P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT

TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: **\$613.70**

PAYMENT DUE BY: **August 25, 2022**

Scheduled Payment: \$613.70 Late Charges: \$0.00
Past Due Payments: \$0.00 Other Fees: \$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received: July 25, 2022
Last Payment Amount: \$613.70

APPLIED TO:

Principal: \$205.80 Interest: \$407.90
Late Fees: \$0.00 Other: \$0.00

Current Balance

\$18,006.20

Total Interest Paid: **\$4,756.90**

Thanks for being a Best Egg customer!

Our Payment Address has changed!

Mail in your payments to:

Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

And...you asked, we listened!

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Tear along this handy-dandy perforated edge.

*This is not the payoff amount.

See Reverse Side For Important Information.

107002-126199-MPMS-72

PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman
Account Number:
44140074

Total Due: **\$613.70**
Due Date: **August 25, 2022**

Please do NOT send cash

- ✓ Make checks payable to "Best Egg"
- ✓ Write your account number on your check
- ✓ Mail 5-7 days ahead for on-time delivery

Best Egg
PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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XXXXXXXXXX0074 0000061370 6

Payment Options

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Mail: Mail us a check to the address below. Please include your Best Egg Account Number in the Memo Line and allow 5-7 business days for your payment to reach us.

Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

Overnight your payment: You can overnight your payment by including your Account Number on the Memo Line on your check to:

Lockbox Services 207865
Best Egg
2975 Regent Blvd
Ste 100
Irving, TX 75063

Best Egg may charge a \$7 processing fee for each payment to customers not enrolled in automatic payments.

General Information

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CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

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CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

Updated Contact Information:

HOME PHONE: _____
BUSINESS PHONE: _____
EMAIL ADDRESS: _____

LVNV33

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: XXXXXXXXXX0074
Statement Date: **August 28, 2022**

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

855-282-6353
CUSTOMER SERVICE
PHONE NUMBER AND
EASTERN HOURS: Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm
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SEND PAYMENT ONLY
TO THIS ADDRESS: Best Egg
P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865
SEND ALL OTHER
CORRESPONDENCE
TO THIS ADDRESS: Best Egg
P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT

TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: **\$1,227.40**
PAYMENT DUE BY: **September 25, 2022**

Scheduled Payment: \$613.70 Late Charges: \$0.00
Past Due Payments: \$613.70 Other Fees: \$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received: July 25, 2022
Last Payment Amount: \$613.70

APPLIED TO:

Principal: \$205.80 Interest: \$407.90
Late Fees: \$0.00 Other: \$0.00

**Current
Balance**
\$18,006.20
Total Interest Paid:
\$4,756.90

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PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman
Account Number:
44140074

Total Due: **\$1,227.40**
Due Date: **September 25, 2022**

Please do NOT send cash

Put a checkmark in this box if you need to update your address or phone number on the back of this coupon.

- ✓ Make checks payable to "Best Egg"
- ✓ Write your account number on your check
- ✓ Mail 5-7 days ahead for on-time delivery

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PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

XXXXXXXXXX0074 0000122740 2

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Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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Best Egg
2975 Regent Blvd
Ste 100
Irving, TX 75063

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BILLING STREET ADDRESS _____

CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

Updated Contact Information:

HOME PHONE: _____

BUSINESS PHONE: _____

EMAIL ADDRESS: _____

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: [REDACTED] 0074

Statement Date: September 28, 2022

**CUSTOMER SERVICE
PHONE NUMBER AND
EASTERN HOURS:** 855-282-6353
Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm
Friday 8am-8pm
Saturday 9am-1pm

**SEND PAYMENT ONLY
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P O Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

**SEND ALL OTHER
CORRESPONDENCE
TO THIS ADDRESS:** Best Egg
P O Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19107

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENTTOTAL AMOUNT DUE: **\$1,841.10**PAYMENT DUE BY: **October 25, 2022**

Scheduled Payment: \$613.70 Late Charges: \$0.00
Past Due Payments: \$1,227.40 Other Fees: \$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received: July 25, 2022
Last Payment Amount: \$613.70

APPLIED TO:

Principal: \$205.80 Interest: \$407.90
Late Fees: \$0.00 Other: \$0.00

**Current
Balance****\$18,006.20**Total Interest Paid:
\$4,756.90

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Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman
Account Number:
44140074

Total Due: **\$1,841.10**
Due Date: **October 25, 2022**

Please do NOT send cash

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- ✓ Make checks payable to "Best Egg"
- ✓ Write your account number on your check
- ✓ Mail 5-7 days ahead for on-time delivery

Best Egg
PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

[REDACTED] 0074 0000184110 7

Payment Options

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CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

BILLING STREET ADDRESS _____

CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

Updated Contact Information:

HOME PHONE: _____

BUSINESS PHONE: _____

EMAIL ADDRESS: _____

LVNV37

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: XXXXXXXXXX0074
Statement Date: **October 28, 2022**

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

CUSTOMER SERVICE PHONE NUMBER AND EASTERN HOURS:	855-282-6353 Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm Friday 8am-8pm Saturday 9am-1pm
SEND PAYMENT ONLY TO THIS ADDRESS:	Best Egg P O Box 207865 Dallas, TX 75320-7865
SEND ALL OTHER CORRESPONDENCE TO THIS ADDRESS:	Best Egg P O Box 42912 Philadelphia, PA 19101

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT

TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: **\$1,268.00**

PAYMENT DUE BY: **November 25, 2022**

Scheduled Payment:	\$317.00	Late Charges:	\$0.00
Past Due Payments:	\$951.00	Other Fees:	\$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received:	July 25, 2022
Last Payment Amount:	\$613.70

APPLIED TO:

Principal:	\$205.80	Interest:	\$407.90
Late Fees:	\$0.00	Other:	\$0.00

**Current
Balance**
\$18,006.20
Total Interest Paid:
\$4,756.90

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PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman	Total Due: \$1,268.00
Account Number: 44140074	Due Date: November 25, 2022

Please do NOT send cash

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Best Egg
PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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Payment Options

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CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

BILLING STREET ADDRESS _____

CITY _____ STATE _____ ZIP _____

Updated Contact Information:

HOME PHONE _____

BUSINESS PHONE: _____

EMAIL ADDRESS _____

LVNV39

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: XXXXXXXXXX 0074
Statement Date: **January 28, 2023**

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

CUSTOMER SERVICE PHONE NUMBER AND EASTERN HOURS:	855-282-6353 Mon-Thurs 8am-10pm Friday 8am-8pm Saturday 9am-1pm
SEND PAYMENT ONLY TO THIS ADDRESS:	Best Egg P O Box 207865 Dallas, TX 75320-7865
SEND ALL OTHER CORRESPONDENCE TO THIS ADDRESS:	Best Egg P O Box 42912 Philadelphia, PA 19101

BEST EGG LOAN ACCOUNT STATEMENT

TOTAL AMOUNT DUE: \$1,268.00
PAYMENT DUE BY: February 25, 2023

Scheduled Payment: \$317.00 Late Charges: \$0.00
Past Due Payments: \$951.00 Other Fees: \$0.00

ACCOUNT PAYMENT SUMMARY

Last Payment Received: December 28, 2022
Last Payment Amount: \$317.00

APPLIED TO:

Principal: \$117.54 Interest: \$199.46
Late Fees: \$0.00 Other: \$0.00

**Current
Balance**
\$17,888.66
Total Interest Paid:
\$5,590.36

Thanks for being a Best Egg customer!

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Best Egg
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Dallas, TX 75320-7865

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107602-126199-MPMS-72

PAYMENT COUPON

Eric Wiseman
Account Number:
44140074

Total Due: **\$1,268.00**
Due Date: **February 25, 2023**

Please do **NOT** send cash

Put a checkmark in this box if you need to update your address or phone number on the back of this coupon.

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Best Egg
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Questions?

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Saturday 9:00 am to 6:00 pm ET

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: [REDACTED] 0074
Statement Date: **February 28, 2023**

SEND PAYMENT ONLY TO THIS ADDRESS:

Best Egg
PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

SEND ALL OTHER CORRESPONDENCE TO THIS ADDRESS:

Best Egg
PO Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

Best Egg Loan Account Statement**Applied To**

Total Amount Due:	\$1,585.00	Principal:	\$117.54	Interest:	\$199.46
Payment Due By:	March 25, 2023	Late Fees:	\$0.00	Other:	\$0.00
Scheduled Payment:	\$317.00				
Past Due Payments:	\$1,268.00				

Account Payment Summary

Last Payment Received:	December 28, 2022	Current Balance*	\$17,888.66
Last Payment Amount:	\$317.00	Total Interest Paid	\$5,590.36

*This is not the payoff amount.

If you received two statements this month, please disregard your previous statement. We previously sent you a statement with an incorrect due date. This reissued statement has your correct due date. We hope we have resolved any confusion!

loan_assistance@mybestegg.com

See Reverse Side For Important Information.

Tear along this handy-dandy perforated edge

107002-126199-MPMS-72

Payment Coupon

Eric Wiseman Total Due: **\$1,585.00**
Account Number: 44140674 Date Due: **March 25, 2023**

- ✔ Make checks payable to "Best Egg"
- ✔ Write your account number on your check
- ✔ Mail 5-7 days ahead for on-time delivery

Please do NOT send cash

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Best Egg
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Dallas, TX 75320-7865

[REDACTED] 0074 0000158500 3

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Important Information

This account balance may be periodically increased due to the addition of accrued interest or other charges as provided in the agreement with the original creditor or otherwise provided by state law. The servicer of this account is Marietta Servicing, LLC, c/o Best Egg, PO Box 42912, Philadelphia, PA 19101. You may contact Best Egg at the address above or by calling 855-282-6353 during our business hours. Our hours of operation are Monday through Thursday 8am to 10pm, Friday 8am to 8pm, and Saturday 9am to 6pm Eastern Time. This communication is from a debt collector. This is an attempt to collect a debt and any information obtained will be used for that purpose.

MASSACHUSETTS RESIDENTS: TO MASSACHUSETTS RESIDENTS: NOTICE OF IMPORTANT RIGHTS. YOU HAVE THE RIGHT TO MAKE A WRITTEN OR ORAL REQUEST THAT TELEPHONE CALLS REGARDING YOUR DEBT NOT BE MADE TO YOU AT YOUR PLACE OF EMPLOYMENT. ANY SUCH ORAL REQUEST WILL BE VALID FOR ONLY TEN (10) DAYS UNLESS YOU PROVIDE WRITTEN CONFIRMATION OF THE REQUEST POSTMARKED OR DELIVERED WITHIN SEVEN (7) DAYS OF SUCH REQUEST. YOU MAY TERMINATE THIS REQUEST BY WRITING TO THE COLLECTION AGENCY. MINNESOTA RESIDENTS: This collection agency is licensed by the Minnesota Department of Commerce.

Address/Phone Number Update

Update your contact information on the lines below and be sure to check the box on the front of this coupon.

Updated Addresses:

Residential Street Address

City

State

Zip

Billing Street Address

City

State

ZIP

Updated Contact Information:

Home Phone

Business Phone

Email Address

loan_assistance@mybestegg.com

855-282-6353 | Monday - Thursday 8am-10pm, Friday 8am-8pm, Saturday 9am-6pm ET

PO Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

Questions?

Call us at **855-282-6353**
Mon to Thurs 8:00 am to 10:00 pm ET
Friday 8:00 am to 8:00 pm ET
Saturday 9:00 am to 6:00 pm ET

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: XXXXXXXXXX 0074
Statement Date: **March 28, 2023**

SEND PAYMENT ONLY TO THIS ADDRESS:

Best Egg
PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

SEND ALL OTHER CORRESPONDENCE TO THIS ADDRESS:

Best Egg
PO Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

Best Egg Loan Account Statement

Total Amount Due: \$1,902.00
Payment Due By: April 25, 2023
Scheduled Payment: \$317.00
Past Due Payments: \$1,585.00

Applied To

Principal: \$117.54 Interest: \$199.46
Late Fees: \$0.00 Other: \$0.00

Account Payment Summary

Last Payment Received: December 28, 2022
Last Payment Amount: \$317.00

Current Balance* \$17,888.66
Total Interest Paid \$5,590.36
*This is not the payoff amount.

loan_assistance@mybestegg.com

See Reverse Side For Important Information.

Tear along this handy-dandy perforated edge

107002-126199-MPMS-72

Payment Coupon

Eric Wiseman Total Due: **\$1,902.00**
Account Number: Date Due: **April 25, 2023**
44140074

- ✔ Make checks payable to "Best Egg"
- ✔ Write your account number on your check
- ✔ Mail 5-7 days ahead for on-time delivery

Please do NOT send cash

Put a checkmark in this box if you need to update your address or phone number on the back of this coupon.

Best Egg
PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

XXXXXXXXXX 0074 0000190200 2

PO Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

Questions?

Call us at 855-282-6353
Mon to Thurs 8:00 am to 10:00 pm ET
Friday 8:00 am to 8:00 pm ET
Saturday 9:00 am to 6:00 pm ET

Payment Options

Pay Automatically: Sign up for automatic payments today! Your monthly payment will be deducted from your bank account and post on your due date.

Online: Log in anytime to BestEgg.com to make, schedule or cancel a payment. Please note that all payments received after 7pm ET won't post to your account until the next business day.

Phone: Call us at 855-282-6353 to make a one-time payment.

Mail: Mail us a check to the address below. Please include your Best Egg Account Number in the Memo Line and allow 5-7 business days for your payment to reach us.

Best Egg
PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

Overnight your payment: You can overnight your payment by including your Account Number on the Memo Line on your check to:

Lockbox Services 207865
Best Egg
2975 Regent Blvd
Ste 100
Irving, TX 75063

General Information

Late Fees: To avoid \$15 late fees on your account, please make your payments on-time and of the minimum payment due.

Other Fees: Nonsufficient Funds Fees and Returned Payment Fees are applied to your account if a payment drafted cannot be completed because the account did not have sufficient funds, or if the payment was returned. To avoid a \$15 fee on your loan, please make sure there are enough funds in your bank account for your monthly payment.

Contact Us

Email: loan_assistance@mybestegg.com
Give us a call at 855-282-6353 during these hours:
Monday - Thursday 8:00am - 10:00pm ET
Friday 8:00am - 8:00pm ET
Saturday 9:00am - 6:00pm ET

Correspondence Address:

Best Egg
PO Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

Credit Bureau Reporting: We may report information about the status of your Best Egg loan to credit bureaus. Late payments, missed payments or other delinquencies on your account may be reflected in your credit report.

Due Date Change: Many customers may be able to change their monthly due date. Give us a call at the number and hours listed above and we can help you out.

Important Information

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Address/Phone Number Update

Update your contact information on the lines below and be sure to check the box on the front of this coupon.

Updated Addresses:

Residential Street Address

City State Zip

Billing Street Address

City State ZIP

Updated Contact Information:

Home Phone

Business Phone

Email Address

loan_assistance@mybestegg.com

855-282-6353 | Monday - Thursday 8am-10pm, Friday 8am-8pm, Saturday 9am-6pm ET

Best Egg
 PO Box 42912
 Philadelphia, PA 19101

LVNV45

Eric Wiseman

Account Number: [REDACTED] 0074

Date: **March 31, 2023**

Eric Wiseman
 4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
 Dublin OH 43017-2751

CHARGE OFF FINAL STATEMENT

Customer Information

Customer Name: Eric Wiseman
 Account Number: 44140074
 Statement Date: March 31, 2023

Last Payment Received

Last Payment Date: 12/28/2022
 Last Payment Amount: \$317.00

Last Payment Amount Applied to:

Principal:	\$117.54	Interest:	\$199.46
Late Fees:	\$0.00	Other:	\$0.00

Account Summary

TOTAL BALANCE DUE: \$17,902.02

Principal Balance: \$17,888.66
 Interest: \$13.36
 Late Fees: \$0.00
 Other: \$0.00

See Reverse Side For Important Information.

Payment Options

Phone: Call us at 855-282-6353 to make a one-time payment.

Mail: Mail us a check to the address below. Please include your Best Egg Account Number in the Memo Line and allow 5-7 business days for your payment to reach us.

Best Egg
PO Box 207865
Dallas, TX 75320-7865

Overnight your payment: You can overnight your payment by including your Account Number on the Memo Line on your check to:

Lockbox Services 207865
Best Egg
2975 Regent Blvd
Ste 100
Irving, TX 75063

General Information

Contact Us:

Email us: Loan_assistance@mybestegg.com
Give us a call at 855-282-6353 during these hours:
Monday - Thursday 8:00am - 10:00pm ET
Friday 8:00am - 8:00pm ET
Saturday 9:00am - 1:00pm ET

Correspondence Address:

Best Egg
PO Box 42912
Philadelphia, PA 19101

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TO MASSACHUSETTS RESIDENTS: NOTICE OF IMPORTANT RIGHTS. YOU HAVE THE RIGHT TO MAKE A WRITTEN OR ORAL REQUEST THAT TELEPHONE CALLS REGARDING YOUR DEBT NOT BE MADE TO YOU AT YOUR PLACE OF EMPLOYMENT. ANY SUCH ORAL REQUEST WILL BE VALID FOR ONLY TEN (10) DAYS UNLESS YOU PROVIDE WRITTEN CONFIRMATION OF THE REQUEST POSTMARKED OR DELIVERED WITHIN SEVEN (7) DAYS OF SUCH REQUEST. YOU MAY TERMINATE THIS REQUEST BY WRITING TO THE COLLECTION AGENCY.

MINNESOTA RESIDENTS:

This collection agency is licensed by the Minnesota Department of Commerce.

April 20, 2023

Eric Wiseman
4273 John Shields Pkwy Ste 104
Dublin OH 43017-2751

RE: Account: ██████████0074
Charge Off Balance: \$17,902.02
Current Balance: \$17,902.02
Last Payment Date: 12/28/2022
Last Payment Amount: \$317.00

Dear Eric Wiseman,

Your Best Egg® loan ending in 0074 has been sold to Sherman Originator III LLC.

Sherman Originator III LLC's contact information is as follows:

Sherman Originator III LLC
c/o Resurgent Capital Services LP
55 Beattie Place, Suite 110
Greenville, SC 29601

Sherman Originator III LLC c/o Resurgent Capital Services LP may also be reached by phone at 1-888-665-0374 or their website is <https://www.resurgent.com/resolve>.

If you have already sent a payment to Best Egg®, the payment will be forwarded to Sherman Originator III LLC.

Please contact Sherman Originator III LLC for assistance with any future servicing needs.

Sincerely,

Best Egg®

FileName	LineNumber	open_dt	Product_Type	subpool_id	app_fico	fico_score_update
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	796	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	797	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	798	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	799	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	800	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	801	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	802	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	803	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	804	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	805	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	806	08/26/2021	Unsecured loan	454	687	783
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	807	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	808	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	809	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	810	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	811	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	812	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	813	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	814	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	815	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410	816	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

BILL OF SALE**DATED AS OF THE CLOSING DATE**

Seller(s) listed below (each a "Seller" and, collectively the "Sellers"), for value received and pursuant to the Forward Flow Account Purchase Agreement, dated as of May 21, 2018 (the "Agreement"), between Marlette Servicing LLC, as Servicer on behalf of Sellers identified therein, and Sherman Originator III LLC as buyer, hereby assign(s), effective as of the Closing Date(s) listed on the Attachment hereto, all rights, title and interest of Seller(s) (and including for the avoidance of doubt, all rights, title and interest of the trustee or other agent of each Seller listed on the Attachment, if any, not in their individual capacities, but solely in their capacity of trustee or other agent of the Seller, who is holding legal title to the Accounts for the benefit of the Seller in such capacity) in and to those Accounts listed on the Attachment and identified in the attached loan file(s). Capitalized terms used herein and not otherwise defined shall have the meanings scribed to such terms in the Agreement.

SELLER(S):

1st Capital Bank
 Auto Club Trust, FSB
 BAWAG
 Blackthorn 2018-A
 Blackthorn Borrower Trust
 CL Trust II
 Community First Bank
 Congressional Bank
 Cross River Bank
 Customers Bank
 Delaware Loan Purchase Trust - I
 DL Investment Sarl
 Exigent Consumer Credit Fund LP
 First Freedom Bank
 Four Corners Community Bank
 Goldman Sachs Bank USA
 Hudson River Trust 2017-2
 Hudson River Trust 2017-3
 IBI Consumer Credit, LP
 Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2020 M-1
 Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2020-1
 Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2020-2
 Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2020-3
 Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2021-M-1
 Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2021-M-2
 Loan Asset Holdings Trust II 2020-1
 Loan Asset Holdings Trust II 2021-1
 Loan Asset Holdings Trust II 2022-1
 MAPT 2019-09A
 MAPT 2019-11A

MAPT 2019-12A
MAPT 2020-10A
MAPT 2020-1A
MAPT 2021-09A
Marlette Funding Consumer Loan Trust
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2017-3
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018-1
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018-2
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018-3
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018-4
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019-1
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019-2
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019-3
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019-4
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2020-1
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2020-2
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2021-1
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2021-2
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2021-3
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2022-1
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2022-2
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2022-3
Marlette Funding Trust
MCL Borrower Trust
MF Trust 2015-A
MPL Trust I
MPLI Capital Holdings II
National Education Loan Network, Inc
Nelnet Unsecured Personal Loan Trust II
Pagaya Acquisition Trust
Pagaya Acquisition Trust II
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2021-4
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2021-5
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-1
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-2
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-3
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-4
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-5
Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-1
Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-2
Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-3
Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-HG1
Pagaya Funding Trust
Pagaya Funding Trust II
Phoenix Value P2P, LP
PML Trust I
Red Marble Trust
Seacoast National Bank
SPC Receivables Funding Trust I
Stone Ridge Alternative Lending Risk Premium Fund US Holdings III LLC

Theorem Grantor Trust 2022-2
Theorem Grantor Trust 2022-3
Theorem Main Master Fund LP
Theorem Prime + Yield Fund Master LP
Theorem Short Duration Liquidity Fund LP
Trallem 2 Trust
Trallem Trust

By: Marlette Servicing, LLC,
as Attorney in Fact

By: Alex Rhodes

Title: Chief Operating Officer

Date: As of the Closing Date listed on the Attachment

TRUSTEE(S) OR OTHER AGENT(S): See Matrix below

SELLER	TRUSTEE OR OTHER AGENT	FILE NAME(S)	UNITS	BALANCES	CLOSING DATE
1st Capital Bank		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
Auto Club Trust, FSB		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
BAWAG		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
Blackthorn 2018- A		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
Blackthorn Borrower Trust		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
CL Trust II		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
Community First Bank		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
Congressional Bank		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
Cross River Bank		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
Customers Bank		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
Delaware Loan Purchase Trust - I		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
DL Investment Sarl		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
Exigent Consumer Credit Fund LP		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
First Freedom Bank		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023
Four Corners Community Bank		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv			4/14/2023

Goldman Sachs Bank USA	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Hudson River Trust 2017-2	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Hudson River Trust 2017-3	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
IBI Consumer Credit, LP	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2020 M-1	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2020-1	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2020-2	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2020-3	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2021-M-1	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2021-M-2	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Loan Asset Holdings Trust II 2020-1	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Loan Asset Holdings Trust II 2021-1	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Loan Asset Holdings Trust II 2022-1	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
MAPT 2019-09A	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023

MAPT 2019-11A		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
MAPT 2019-12A		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
MAPT 2020-10A		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
MAPT 2020-01A		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
MAPT 2021-09A		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Consumer Loan Trust		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2017-3		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018- 1		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018- 2		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018- 3		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018- 4		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019-1		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	4/14/2023

Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019- 2		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019- 3		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019- 4		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2020- 1		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2020-2		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2021- 1		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2021- 2		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2021- 3		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2022- 1		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2022-2				
Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2022-3		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023

Marlette Funding Trust		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
MCL Borrower Trust		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
MF Trust 2015-A		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
MPL Trust I		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
MPLI Capital Holdings II		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
National Education Loan Network, Inc		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Nelnet Unsecured Personal Loan Trust II		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya Acquisition Trust		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya Acquisition Trust II		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2021-4		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023

Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2021-5		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-1		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-2		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-3		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-4		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-5		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-1		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-2		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-3		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-HG1		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Pagaya Funding Trust		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023

Pagaya Funding Trust II		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Phoenix Value P2P, LP		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
PML Trust I		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Red Marble Trust		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Seacoast National Bank		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
SPC Receivables Funding Trust I		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Stone Ridge Alternative Lending Risk Premium Fund US Holdings III LLC		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Theorem Grantor Trust 2022-2		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Theorem Grantor Trust 2022-3		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Theorem Main Master Fund LP		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Theorem Prime + Yield Fund Master LP		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023
Theorem Short Duration Liquidity Fund LP		CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv		4/14/2023

Trallem 2 Trust	[REDACTED]	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	[REDACTED]	4/14/2023
Trallem Trust	[REDACTED]	CHARGEOFF_SALE_S HER_20230410.csv	[REDACTED]	4/14/2023

[REDACTED]

Declaration of Account Transfer

Sherman Originator III LLC ("SOLLC III"), without recourse, to the extent permitted by applicable law, transferred, sold, assigned, conveyed, granted and delivered to Sherman Originator LLC ("SOLLC") all of its right, title and interest in and to the receivables and other assets (the "Assets") identified on Exhibit A, in the Receivable File dated April 10, 2023 delivered by 1st Capital Bank, Auto Club Trust, FSB, BAWAG, Blackthorn 2018-A, Blackthorn Borrower Trust, CL Trust II, Community First Bank, Congressional Bank, Cross River Bank, Customers Bank, Delaware Loan Purchase Trust - I, DL Investment Sarl, Exigent Consumer Credit Fund LP, First Freedom Bank, Four Corners Community Bank, Goldman Sachs Bank USA, Hudson River Trust 2017-2, Hudson River Trust 2017-3, I.B.I Consumer Credit, LP, Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2020-1, Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2020-2, Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2020-3, Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2021-M-1, Loan Asset Holdings Trust 2021-M-2, Loan Asset Holdings Trust II 2020-1, Loan Asset Holdings Trust II 2022-1, Loan Assets Holding Trust II 2021-1, Loan Assets Holdings Trust 2020 M-1, MAPT 2019-09A, MAPT 2019-11A, MAPT 2019-12A, MAPT 2020-10A, MAPT 2020-1A, MAPT 2021-09A, Marlette Funding Consumer Loan Trust, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2017-3, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018-1, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018-2, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018-3, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2018-4, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019-1, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019-2, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019-3, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2019-4, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2020-1, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2020-2, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2021-01, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2021-2, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2021-3, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2022-1, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2022-2, Marlette Funding Grantor Trust 2022-3, Marlette Funding Trust, MCL Borrower Trust, MF Trust 2015-A, MPL Trust I, MPLI Capital Holdings II, National Education Loan Network, Inc, Nelnet Unsecured Personal Loan Trust II, Pagaya Acquisition Trust, Pagaya Acquisition Trust II, Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2021-4, Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2021-5, Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022- 1, Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-2, Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-3, Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-4, Pagaya AI Debt Grantor Trust 2022-5, Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-1, Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-2, Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-3, Pagaya AI Debt Selection Grantor Trust 2021-HG1, Pagaya Funding Trust, Pagaya Funding Trust II, Phoenix Value P2P, LP, PML Trust I, Red Marble Trust, Seacoast National Bank, SPC Receivables Funding Trust I, Stone Ridge Alt Lnding Risk Prem Fnd US Hldngs III, Theorem Grantor Trust 2022-2, Theorem Grantor Trust 2022-3, Theorem Main Master Fund LP, Theorem Prime + Yield Fund Master LP, Theorem Short Duration Liquidity Fund LP, Trallem 2 Trust, Trallem Trust on April 14, 2023 for purchase by SOLLC III on April 14, 2023. The transfer of the Assets included electronically stored business records.

SOLLC, subsequent to the above mentioned transfer, transferred, sold, assigned, conveyed, granted and delivered to LVNV Funding LLC ("LVNV"), the above mentioned Assets. The transfer of the Assets included electronically stored business records.

Declaration of Account Transfer

Sherman Originator III LLC
a Delaware Limited Liability Company

By:
Name: Jon Mazzoni
Title: Director

Sherman Originator LLC
a Delaware Limited Liability Company

By:
Name: Jackson Walker
Title: Authorized Representative

LVNV Funding LLC
a Delaware Limited Liability Company

By:
Name: Daniel Picciano
Title: Authorized Representative

Exhibit A**Receivables File****04.14.23 CHARGEOFF_SALE_SHER_20230410**

Transfer Group	Portfolio	Transfer Batch
906249	41656	N/A

**IN THE COURT OF COMMON PLEAS
FRANKLIN COUNTY, OHIO**

LVNV FUNDING, LLC

*

CASE NO. 24CV000841

PLAINTIFF

v.

*

**PLAINTIFF'S RESPONSES TO
DEFENDANT'S FIRST
REQUESTS FOR ADMISSIONS**

ERIC WISEMAN

DEFENDANT

*

Now comes Plaintiff, by counsel, and provides the following responses to Defendant's Requests for Admissions.

REQUEST NUMBER 1: Plaintiff is familiar with the federal Fair Debt Collection Practices Act.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 2: Plaintiff is not familiar with the federal Fair Debt Collection Practices Act.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 3: Defendant is a "consumer" as that term is defined in 15 USCA § 1692a.

RESPONSE: After reasonable inquiry, the information known or readily available is insufficient to enable Plaintiff to admit or deny this request.

REQUEST NUMBER 4: All of Plaintiff's communications to Defendant include the

phrase "this is a communication from a debt collector."

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff did not send communications to Defendant. Plaintiff is a passive holding entity.

REQUEST NUMBER 5: All of Plaintiff's communications to Defendant do not include the phrase "this is a communication from a debt collector."

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff did not send communications to Defendant. Plaintiff is a passive holding entity.

REQUEST NUMBER 6: The phrase "debt collector" in Plaintiff's communications means the same as "debt collector" as defined in 15 USCA § 1692a.

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff did not send communications to Defendant. Plaintiff is a passive holding entity.

REQUEST NUMBER 7: Plaintiff's filings in this case include the phrase "this is a communication from a debt collector."

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff did not send communications to Defendant. Plaintiff is a passive holding entity.

REQUEST NUMBER 8: Plaintiff's filings in this case do not include the phrase "this is a communication from a debt collector."

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff did not send communications to Defendant. Plaintiff is a passive holding entity.

REQUEST NUMBER 9: The phrase "debt collector" in Plaintiff's filings means the same as "debt collector" as defined in 15 USCA § 1692a.

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff did not send communications to Defendant. Plaintiff is a passive holding entity.

REQUEST NUMBER 10: Plaintiff's communications to Defendant state that Plaintiff is "attempting to collect a debt."

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff did not send communications to Defendant. Plaintiff is a passive holding entity.

REQUEST NUMBER 11: Plaintiff's communications to Defendant do not state that Plaintiff is "attempting to collect a debt."

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff did not send communications to Defendant. Plaintiff is a passive holding entity.

REQUEST NUMBER 12: The term "debt" in Plaintiff's communications means the same as "debt" as defined in 15 USCA § 1692a.

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff did not send communications to Defendant. Plaintiff is a passive holding entity.

REQUEST NUMBER 13: Plaintiff's filings in this case state that Plaintiff is "attempting to collect a debt."

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff did not send communications to Defendant. Plaintiff is a passive holding entity.

REQUEST NUMBER 14: Plaintiff's filings in this case do not state that Plaintiff is "attempting to collect a debt."

RESPONSE: Denied, as the court filings speak for themselves, and not all filings are an attempt to collect".

REQUEST NUMBER 15: The term "debt" in Plaintiff's filings means the same as "debt" as defined in 15 USCA § 1692a.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 16: Any sums that are allegedly owed on the Account constitutes a "debt," as that term is defined in 15 USCA § 1692a.

RESPONSE: After reasonable inquiry, the information known or readily available is insufficient to enable Plaintiff to admit or deny this request.

REQUEST NUMBER 17: Plaintiff is a "debt collector" as that term is defined in 15 USCA § 1692a.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 18: Defendant had an Account with a bank, a credit card company, or another entity ("third-party entity").

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 19: Plaintiff is not the Original Creditor.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 20: If the Original Creditor is prohibited from collecting the debt, then Plaintiff (as an assignee) is prohibited from collecting the debt.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 21: Plaintiff furnished no goods or services to the Defendant which resulted in any portion of the amount claimed.

RESPONSE: Denied as Plaintiff “stands in the shoes” of the original creditor via assignment and transfer of the account.

REQUEST NUMBER 22: Some or all of the amount claimed is not legally collectible under the laws of the State of Ohio.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 23: The Account was in default on the date Plaintiff was allegedly assigned the debt.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 24: At least a portion of the amount claimed in this lawsuit includes fees (late fees, over-limit fees, or any other fees) charged by the Original Creditor.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 25: The amount claimed in this lawsuit includes costs of collection charged by the Original Creditor.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 26: At least a portion of the amount claimed in this lawsuit includes fees (late fees, over-limit fees, or any other fees) charged by an Intervening Creditor.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 27: The amount claimed in this lawsuit includes costs of collection charged by an Intervening Creditor.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 28: The amount claimed in this lawsuit includes interest that had accrued to the Original Creditor.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 29: The amount claimed in this lawsuit includes interest that had accrued to an Intervening Creditor.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 30: The entire amount claimed in this lawsuit includes transactions occurring more than eight (8) years prior to the date suit was filed in this matter.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 31: The initial communication by Plaintiff to Defendant did not include any notification of validation, which is required by 15 USCA § 1692g.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 32: A third-party entity allegedly assigned the Account to Plaintiff.

RESPONSE: Admitted that the account was assigned and transferred to Plaintiff, and Plaintiff owns all rights and title to the account.

REQUEST NUMBER 33: There is no signed application or contract in Plaintiff's possession, custody, or control for the repayment of the amount claimed.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 34: There is no written agreement between Plaintiff and Defendant for the payment of interest on the amount claimed.

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff stands in the shoes of the original creditor via assignment and transfer of the account.

REQUEST NUMBER 35: There is no written agreement between Plaintiff and Defendant for the payment of fees (late fees, over-limit fees, or any other fees) on the amount claimed.

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff stands in the shoes of the original creditor via

assignment and transfer of the account.

REQUEST NUMBER 36: There is no written agreement between Plaintiff and Defendant for the payment of costs of collection on the amount claimed.

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff stands in the shoes of the original creditor via assignment and transfer of the account. Moreover, Plaintiff does not seek “costs of collection”.

REQUEST NUMBER 37: There is no written agreement between Plaintiff and Defendant providing for the payment to Plaintiff of attorney fees for the collection of the amount claimed.

RESPONSE: Denied, as Plaintiff stands in the shoes of the original creditor via assignment and transfer of the account. Moreover, Plaintiff does not seek “attorney fees for the collection”.

REQUEST NUMBER 38: There is no written assignment in Plaintiff's possession, custody, or control for the amount claimed.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 39: There is a written assignment in Plaintiff's possession, custody, or control for the amount claimed.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 40: There is a written purchase and sale agreement, forward

flow agreement, receivables sale agreement, or some other type of written agreement that governs the terms of the alleged transfer or assignment of Defendant's account to Plaintiff.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 41: Plaintiff understands what is a forward-flow agreement.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 42: Plaintiff understands what is a purchase and sale agreement.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 43: Plaintiff understands what is a receivables sale agreement.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 44: Plaintiff has never produced to Defendant a copy of any purchase and sale agreement.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial, and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 45: Plaintiff has never produced to Defendant an unredacted copy of any purchase and sale agreement.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial, and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 46: Plaintiff has never produced to Defendant a copy of any forward-flow agreement.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial, and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 47: Plaintiff has never produced to Defendant an unredacted copy of any forward-flow agreement.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial, and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 48: Plaintiff has never produced to Defendant a copy of any receivables sale agreement.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial, and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 49: Plaintiff has never produced to Defendant an unredacted copy of any receivables sale agreement.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial, and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 50: At one time, there existed an unredacted and unmodified electronic data file (e.g., excel spreadsheet, database, or other electronic file with stored

data) that included Defendant's account information.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 51: There exists an unredacted and unmodified electronic data file (e.g., excel spreadsheet, database, or other electronic file with stored data) that includes Defendant's account information.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 52: There does not exist an unredacted or unmodified electronic data file (e.g., excel spreadsheet, database, or other electronic file with stored data) that includes Defendant's account information.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 53: Defendant's account information was in an electronic data file that included account information for other alleged debtors.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 54: Defendant's account information was in an electronic data file that included account information for other alleged debtors, and Plaintiff has possession, custody, or control of that electronic data file.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 55: Defendant's account information was in an electronic data file that included account information for other alleged debtors, but Plaintiff does not have possession, custody, or control of that electronic data file.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 56: Defendant's account information was in an electronic data file, which was in Plaintiff's possession, custody, or control at one time, and which included account information for other alleged debtors.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 57: Defendant's account information was in an electronic data file that included account information for other alleged debtors, but Plaintiff never had possession, custody, or control of that electronic data file.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 58: Plaintiff has possession, custody, or control of an unredacted and unmodified electronic data file (e.g., excel spreadsheet, database, or other electronic file with stored data) that includes Defendant's account information.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 59: Plaintiff does not have possession, custody, or control of an unredacted or unmodified electronic data file (e.g., excel spreadsheet, database, or other electronic file with stored data) that includes Defendant's account information.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 60: Plaintiff's acquisition of Defendant's account included a transfer of an electronic data file with Defendant's account information.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 61: Plaintiff's acquisition of Defendant's account included a transfer of an electronic data file with Defendant's account information, along with account information for other alleged debtors.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 62: Plaintiff has never produced to Defendant an unredacted or unmodified electronic data file that had Defendant's account information.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial, and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 63: There were no dealings between Plaintiff and the Defendant that resulted in the principal of the amount claimed.

RESPONSE:

REQUEST NUMBER 64: Within the twelve (12) months prior to the filing of this action, Plaintiff have filed at least one hundred (100) lawsuits against individuals for debt allegedly owed, for which Plaintiff were not the Original Creditor.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial, and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 65: Plaintiff is aware that Plaintiff's Complaint has no basis in

law or fact.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 66: Plaintiff has been sued previously for a violation of the Fair Debt Collection Practices Act.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial, and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 67: Plaintiff has been sued previously on multiple occasions for violations of the Fair Debt Collection Practices Act.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial, and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 68: Plaintiff are not the Original Creditor of the debt claimed in this action.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 69: Plaintiff are not the Original Creditor of the Account sued upon.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 70: Plaintiff cannot determine with specificity how much of the amount claimed is principal.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 71: Plaintiff cannot determine with specificity how much of the amount claimed is interest.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 72: Plaintiff cannot determine with specificity how much of the amount claimed is fees (late fees, over-limit fees, or any other fees).

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 73: Plaintiff cannot determine with specificity how much of the amount claimed is costs of collection.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 74: Plaintiff conducted no independent investigation concerning the validity of the debt prior to filing this action.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 75: Plaintiff has not produced to the Defendant the “assignment” as referenced and incorporated by Plaintiff’s Complaint.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 76: Plaintiff have been sued in the past for violations of the Fair Debt Collection Practices Act or the Fair Credit Reporting Act.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information.

This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 77: Plaintiff have not requested any other entity to independently verify the debt underlying the amount claimed prior to filing the Lawsuit.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 78: Plaintiff have no personal knowledge concerning the goods or services that were purchased (if any) by Defendant, which make up the principal portion of the amount claimed.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 79: Plaintiff have not taken actions to verify that the amount claimed is accurate.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 80: Plaintiff either purchased or re-purchased the debt for less than Ten (10) cents on the dollar.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 81: Plaintiff regularly collect debts after acquiring or reacquiring the debt from a third party.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 82: Plaintiff represented to Defendant that the amount claimed was legally collectible under the laws of the State of Ohio.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 83: Plaintiff's attorneys are required to comply with the Fair Debt Collection Practices Act.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 84: Plaintiff has written policies that are designed to prevent violations of the Fair Debt Collection Practices Act.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 85: Plaintiff does not have written policies relating to the Fair Debt Collection Practices Act.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 86: Plaintiff has implemented procedures that are designed to prevent violations of the Fair Debt Collection Practices Act.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 87: Plaintiff has not implemented procedures relating to the Fair Debt Collection Practices Act.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 88: Plaintiff's attorneys reviewed all of the documents and evidence that showed the alleged transfer of Defendant's account to Plaintiff.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 89: Plaintiff's attorneys never reviewed all of the documents and evidence that showed the alleged transfer of Defendant's account to Plaintiff.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 90: Prior to filing this lawsuit, Plaintiff's attorneys reviewed an electronic data file that included Defendant's account information and other alleged debtors' account information.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 91: Prior to filing this lawsuit, Plaintiff's attorneys did not review an electronic data file that included Defendant's account information and other

alleged debtors' account information.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 92: Prior to filing this lawsuit, Plaintiff's attorneys reviewed a written contract that allegedly transferred ownership of Defendant's account to Plaintiff.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 93: Plaintiff's attorneys reviewed a multi-page written contract that allegedly transferred ownership of Defendant's account to Plaintiff.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 94: Prior to filing this lawsuit, Plaintiff's attorneys did not review any multi-page written contract that allegedly transferred ownership of Defendant's account to Plaintiff.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 95: Defendant's account was part of a Portfolio.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 96: Plaintiff purchased a Portfolio that allegedly included Defendant's account.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 97: Plaintiff purchased a Portfolio that allegedly included Defendant's account but paid less than ten percent (10%) of the face value of the Portfolio.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 98: Plaintiff purchased the Portfolio that allegedly included Defendant's account but paid less than five percent (5%) of the face value of the Portfolio.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 99: Plaintiff purchased the Portfolio that allegedly included Defendant's account, but paid less than two percent (2%) of the face value of the Portfolio.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 100: Plaintiff purchased the Portfolio that allegedly included Defendant's account, knowing fully that some of the accounts in the Portfolio were uncollectable.

RESPONSE: Admitted that Plaintiff purchased the portfolio that included Defendant's account, but the balance of this request is denied.

REQUEST NUMBER 101: When Plaintiff purchased the Portfolio that allegedly included Defendant's account, Plaintiff did not know whether or not Defendant could legally collect any alleged debt from Defendant's account.

RESPONSE: Admitted that Plaintiff purchased the Portfolio that included Defendant's account, but the balance of this request is denied.

REQUEST NUMBER 102: When Plaintiff purchased the Portfolio that allegedly included Defendant's account, Plaintiff did know whether or not Defendant's account was even a part of that Portfolio.

RESPONSE: Admitted that Plaintiff purchased the Portfolio that included Defendant's account, but the balance of this request is denied.

REQUEST NUMBER 103: Admit that the Plaintiff has policies and procedures in place to prevent bona fide errors in false misrepresentations.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 104: Admit that the Plaintiff has failed to adhere to the policies

and procedures in place to prevent bona fide errors in false misrepresentations.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 105: Admit that the Plaintiff's Complaint, includes intentional misleading statements.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 106: Admit that Plaintiff intentionally did not attach the complete chain of title.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 107: Admit that Plaintiff employs call centers in their debt collection practices.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 108: Admit that Plaintiff employed call centers in their debt collection practices, who contacted the Defendant in the course of the Plaintiff's collection attempts.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 109: Admit that the calls of the call centers, who are agents of the Plaintiff, have all their calls recorded.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 110: Admit that the calls of the call centers, who are agents of the Plaintiff, who have contacted the Defendant in attempts to collect the debt have had their calls recorded.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 111: Admit that the Plaintiff's Complaint references "File No. 23-120249."

RESPONSE: Admitted that the Complaint speaks for itself.

REQUEST NUMBER 112: Admit that the "File No. 23-120249," referenced in the Plaintiff's Complaint, contains all the files the Plaintiff's Attorney's reviewed in connection with the Account prior to filing the Complaint.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 113: Admit that the "File No. 23-120249," referenced in the Plaintiff's Complaint, does not include the alleged assignment document referenced in the Complaint.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 114: Admit that the Plaintiff's Complaint does not contain the referenced and incorporated assignment document from the Original Creditor and the

Plaintiff.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 115: Admit that the Original Creditor “Cross River Bank” is not the same entity as the Plaintiff.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 116: Admit that the Plaintiff acquired the Account after the account was charged off by the Original Creditor.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 117: Admit that Paragraph 5 of the Plaintiff’s Complaint states that the “ Account was charged-off by the Original Creditor on or about March 31, 2023.”

RESPONSE: Admitted that the Complaint speaks for itself.

REQUEST NUMBER 118: Admit that relief sought, \$17,902.02, includes: a principal amount, interest, interest upon interest, and fees.

RESPONSE: Admitted that the balance owed is itemized in the account statements and includes principal and interest.

REQUEST NUMBER 119: Admit that the Plaintiff has made demands to the Defendant to liquidate the balance of the account.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 120: Admit that the Plaintiff has not made demands to the Defendant to liquidate the balance of the account.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 121: Admit that the Plaintiff know that they can not prevail on both breach of contract and unjust enrichment in their complaint.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 122: Admit that LVNV Funding, LLC ("LVNV") purchases debt in bulk for pennies on the dollar from affiliate entities and attempts to collect on those debts through various other affiliated entities

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 123: Admit that LVNV has been the subject of an enforcement action in Maryland.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 124: Admit that each attorney, in this matter Nathan Allen (OSCR#: 0100653) of Stenger & Stenger, who has signed pleadings or other documents in furtherance of collecting a debt on behalf of Plaintiff is a "debt collector", as defined

in 15 U.S.C. § 1962a(6) .

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information.

This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 125: Admit that Plaintiff has no employees of it's own .

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 126: Admit that Plaintiff attempts to collect those alleged debts by engaging other entities, such as servicers (e.g., Resurgent) or various law firms and attorneys throughout the country.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information.

This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 127: Admit that at the time of filing the Complaint, the Plaintiff did not have in their possession the complete assignment document.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 128: Admit that at the time of filing the Complaint, the Plaintiff did not have in their possession the complete assignment document.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 129: Admit that Plaintiff servicers communicate with Defendant.

RESPONSE:Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 130: Admit that Plaintiff, or agents/servicers of Plaintiff, has made phone calls to the Defendant.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 131: Admit that the “File No. 23-120249,” referenced in the Plaintiff’s Complaint, contains all the information the Plaintiff reviewed prior to filing the Complaint.

RESPONSE: Denied

REQUEST NUMBER 132: Admit that the “File No. 23-120249,” referenced in the Plaintiff’s Complaint, does not contains all the information the Plaintiff reviewed prior to filing the Complaint.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 133: Admit that Plaintiff is a limited liability company that is organized in Delaware, headquartered in Nevada, managed from South Carolina, and registered to do business in Ohio.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 134: Admit that Plaintiff is a limited liability company that is

organized in Delaware.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information.

This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 135: Admit that Plaintiff is a part of an integrated conglomeration of affiliated entities that include: (a) Sherman Capital, LLC and Meeting Street Partners II, Inc., which own and operate Sherman Financial Group ("SFG," which is an integrated financial services company engaged in purchasing and servicing portfolios of consumer debt that SFG acquires at a large discount) and Sherman Capital Markets ("SCM," which provides management services for SFG); (b) Sherman Originators LLC ("Originator," for which Plaintiff is a wholly-owned subsidiary, with Originator being headquartered in South Carolina and, also, being a wholly-owned subsidiary of SFG); (c) Sherman Acquisition Limited Partnership ("SALP"), Sherman Acquisition II Limited Partnership ("SAIILP"), Sherman Acquisition II General Partner LLC ("SAIIGPLLC"), and Sherman Acquisition LLC ("SALLC"), all of which are subsidiaries of SFG; and (d) Resurgent Capital Services Limited Partnership ("Resurgent," which is headquartered in South Carolina and acts as a master servicer for charged-off consumer debt owned by Plaintiff).

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information.

This request is beyond the scope of discovery.

REQUEST NUMBER 136: Admit that Plaintiff routinely instructs the law firms and attorneys on whether or not to accept or reject settlement offers or demands.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information.

This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections. Without waiving objections, denied.

REQUEST NUMBER 137: Admit that Plaintiff attempts to collect those alleged debts through one or more of the alleged enterprises

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. Without waiving objections, denied.

REQUEST NUMBER 138: Admit that Plaintiff performs activities that are either necessary or helpful to the operation of those servicers, law firms, or attorneys (collectively, "enterprises"; individually, "enterprise")

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 139: Admit that Plaintiff performs activities that are either necessary or helpful to the operation of those servicers, law firms, or attorneys (collectively, "enterprises"; individually, "enterprise")

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

REQUEST NUMBER 140: Admit that Plaintiff is a holding entity of the debt.

RESPONSE: Admitted

REQUEST NUMBER 141: Admit that Plaintiff and attorneys are under a contingency fee bases for representation of the collection of the Account.

RESPONSE: Objection. This request is immaterial and seeks irrelevant information. This request is beyond the scope of discovery. This request seeks to invade attorney-client privilege and attorney work product protections.

Respectfully submitted,

/s/Boyd W. Gentry
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CERTIFICATE OF SERVICE

I certify that a copy of the foregoing has been sent by email to Andrew Barnes on July 17, 2024, at the following address: abarnes@abarneslaw.com

/s/Boyd W. Gentry
Boyd W. Gentry (OH#0071057)